

Design of Citizens' Parliaments

Laurence Monnot (COMMIT) and Andrea Sedlaczek (COMMIT)

Contributors: Helmut Peissl (COMMIT), Nico Carpentier (CU),
Vaia Doudaki (CU), Josef Seethaler (OEAW), Rosemary Day (MIC)
and Brankica Petković (MI)

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<i>Author(s)</i>	Laurence Monnot (COMMIT), Andrea Sedlaczek (COMMIT), Helmut Peissl (COMMIT), Nico Carpentier (CU), Vaia Doudaki (CU), Josef Seethaler (OEAW), Rosemary Day (MIC) and Brankica Petković (MI)
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Introduction and executive summary

Deliverable D.6.2 “*Design of citizens’ parliaments*” aims to provide a framework for the Design of the citizens’ parliaments that will be organized by the WP6 partners COMMIT, CU, MIC, MI face-to-face in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia and later, based on their results, online and as a scientific experiment by OEAW in Germany.

While the implementation of the Citizens' Parliaments (CPs) is part of the MeDeMAP research project, for the partners and local citizens involved, it is also a socio-political and learning action with an impact on them and on the local context.

D6.2 seeks to answer the research question “*How to conceptualize and organize a citizens’ parliament?*” with the approach of Participatory Action Research (PAR). It is designed as a practical guide for the implementation of the CPs and for the subsequent data analysis in view of MeDeMAP tasks 6.3 (Analysis of the sessions and final decisions of citizens’ parliaments) and 6.4 (Evaluation of PAR research).

D6.2 corresponds to MeDeMAP Task 6.2 “*Implementation of Citizens' Parliaments in the local context of the countries covered*”. As specified in the Grant Agreement p. 28, “*the design (is) based on results of Task 6.1 and reflection on components of the PAR cycle (Participation Action Research cycle)*”. Besides the lessons learnt from the *Research Report on Successful Practice of Policy Development with Citizens’ Parliaments in Europe* (Deliverable 6.1) concerning the design of CPs, the content of the CP sessions draws on the results of the other MeDeMAP packages.

This document includes guidelines and also descriptions of steps that have already been implemented by the WP6 partners. A large part of the corpus consists of annexes, hence the hybrid form of what is not a report but a pilot document.

Part 1 presents organizational steps to follow before the implementation. Part 2 focuses on the implementation stage with its learning phase and facilitation. Part 3 provides indications for the research design for data collection and analysis.

The annexes compiled with the contribution of CU, OEAW, MIC and MI are intended to present guidelines (e.g. expert briefing, learning objectives, research questions) or offer some models, such as the CP scripts of COMMIT and CU.

1 CP design and organization

As specified in the Grant Agreement, the design of the CPs is based on the results of Task 6.1, i.e. the *Research Report on Successful Practice of Policy Development with Citizens' Parliaments in Europe* (Deliverable 6.1) and on reflection on components of the PAR cycle outlined in Carpentier & Wimmer (2024a).

The content of the CP learning phases of the CP sessions draws on the results of the other MeDeMAP packages.

After reviewing historical models and good practices of citizens' parliaments in Europe, Deliverable 6.1 recalls that current CPs are a hybrid construction, borrowing features from different models. As stated in the OECD comparative study conducted in 2020 on nearly 300 cases (organized or initiated by public institutions) „*the process of choosing and tailoring the most appropriate representative deliberative model for a given context, level of government, phase of the policy cycle, and policy issue at hand is a creative one, with opportunities to combine features from different models* “. The international organization further underlines that “*it is of essence to ensure that all fundamental phases of a representative deliberative process are preserved: learning, deliberation, and developing informed collective recommendations*” (OECD, 2020, p. 62).

The design proposed in D6.2 builds on the lessons presented in section 3.4 of D6.1, and is also inspired by the quality standards developed over the last thirty years and resumed as 'principles' in OECD (2020).

These lessons are recalled throughout Part 1 of this deliverable. The main recommendations and also the constraints of the MeDeMAP CPs can be briefly recalled here.

Constraints: The topic of Media and Democracy is complex; the budget is tight; the CPs will be a socio-political action embedded in a specific local context and at the same time a scientific experience whose process and results must be comparable; both the process and the data collection must follow a participatory approach.

The main quality criteria advocated by OECD (2020) are

- The CP should include the following phases: a learning phase with experts; a deliberation phase, a phase dedicated to the adoption of the outcomes, a closure.
- It should have a purpose related to a public issue;
- The process should be transparent
- The recruitment of participants should achieve representativeness and inclusiveness;
- Sound group deliberation should be ensured

Furthermore, the OECD estimates that four days is the minimum for a CP on a complex topic “*to allow citizens adequate time and resources to develop considered and detailed collective recommendations*” (OECD, 2020, p. 34).

1.1 The national project teams

Unlike large citizens' assemblies with a generous budget, where many teams have different duties and functions (DemocracyNext, 2025, 3 January), the WP6 partners are both the commissioner and the operator. With the help of the Support group/Advisory board, they will

plan and implement the communication, control the content and format of the learning phase and participate in the facilitation. Data collection and analysis will also be carried out internally by the WP6 partners.

The project team will also be the point of contact for participants, for the support group and for external contacts. It's important to define the roles of the team members in advance. A distinction should be made between organizational and facilitation tasks and the task of monitoring the process as a whole.

Main tasks and human resources involved

- Two facilitators: a main facilitator and a second facilitator (or more)
- Two observers: Each of them in charge of compiling field notes for one research question
- Team members responsible for logistics
- Team members responsible for collecting data and uploading documents to the CP platform
- Team members responsible for blog posts
- Team members responsible for transcription, analysis and writing of national report

Facilitators: The plenary and small group discussions will be facilitated by two people (or three in Ireland), a main facilitator (also called moderator in some annexes) and a co-facilitator. In Austria and Slovenia, the main facilitator will be a professional hired for the occasion, while in the Czech Republic and Ireland, it will be an experienced team member.

The tasks of presenting content issues or reminding the participants to consult the documentation or fill out the feedback survey, express opinions of confirmation or dissent, etc. will be done by a WP6 team member.

Observers: There will be two observers in the room with no role other than ethnographic observation. They will focus on collecting data in the form of field notes for the two research questions. CU will train the observers online on 25 February 2025.

Apart from the field notes by the observers, team members are responsible for other data collected during and after the CPs, i.e. the final resolutions; posters and flip charts (in some cases including drawings from graphic reports); minutes of the CP meetings; audio recordings; online surveys and interviews with a selection of participants (after the end of the CP). There will be no video recording.

Team members are also responsible for selective transcripts of the audio recordings, the analysis and the writing of the national report (see section 3.3).

1.2 Structure and content of the CPs

The CP sessions will take place on four Saturdays between March and May 2025, followed by a presentation of the results at the national level in June. In each session, a targeted number of 20 citizens will learn, deliberate and decide on resolutions.

Each CP session will be devoted to a topic:

- CP1: Media and Democracy and overview of the CP objectives and process
- CP2: Media systems and media regulation
- CP3 or CP4: Representation in the media
- CP3 or CP4: Participation in/through the media

More details of the content can be found in the Learning Objectives in Annex 2. They are based on lessons learned from other MeDeMAP packages.

There were two main options for the structure of the process:

Option 1: To go through all the topics from the beginning, with the first session dedicated to learning, followed by day sessions for deliberation and later sessions for decision-making. It would have been more difficult for citizens to focus with the same depth on a topic and there would have been no iterative path between the phases of learning, reflecting, deliberating and adopting resolutions.

For these reasons, the option adopted is a script structured around the topics. Each day session will be devoted to one topic. Following a PAR approach as outlined by Carpentier & Wimmer (2024a), each session will follow the same common thread: check-in & introduction, learning phase with expert inputs and inputs from MeDeMAP, reflection on the learning, deliberation on (CP1)/refinement of (CP2,CP3, CP4) topics to prioritize, draft of resolutions (for CP2,CP3, CP4), adoption of resolutions (CP2,CP3, CP4). This allows for a smoother circular relationship between the learning, deliberation and adoption phases. A facilitation team will guide participants through these stages, alternating between small groups and plenary sessions.

20 citizens	2-3 moderators, 2 observers, experts
4 Sessions on Saturdays March-May 25	(Dates for CP Austria) 1. Sat. 22.3: Media & Democracy 2. Sat. 5.4: Media systems & media regulation 3. Sat. 26.4: Participation <i>in</i> and <i>through</i> the media 4. Sat. 17.5: Representation in the media and Closure
Sequences	
Check-in and presentation	CP1: Presentation of MeDeMAP. Presentation of CP: objectives, agenda and topics. CP2, 3,4: Check-in and objectives for the day. Introducing the experts.
Learning phase	Expert inputs, Videos, Q&A
Reflection on learning and (re)defining the sub-topics	Small groups work to define the subtopics to be addressed. Experts are available for further questions.

Draft of resolutions	Small groups draft resolutions. Resolutions are refined. Resolutions adopted in plenary.
Wrap-up, check-out & info on follow-up	Participants are informed about follow-up and about the survey and expression of approval/disapproval to be completed on the CP platform. (CP4 information on national presentation event in June 2025 and European presentation in Brussels 2026)
<i>After the CPs</i>	
National event (June 2025)	Presentation of resolutions/recommendations to media and political stakeholders and to the broader public
European event (January or February 2026)	Presentations as part of WP7 dissemination in Brussels (participation of 2 citizens per national CP)

1.3 Participants

WP6 partners aim to recruit 20 participants for each CP by the end of February 2025. A higher number should be selected to create a reserve list (see Annex 14 Methodological guidelines).

The German foundation Bertelsmann Stiftung (2025) advises to start recruiting at least six weeks before the event and to over-recruit by almost 15% to ensure the final participation of the expected number of participants. A preselection of 23 to 25 applicants should ensure to retain 20 participants on Day 2 of the CPs.

The three main steps are information, recruitment and selection of participants and, at a later stage, consolidation of the list of participants and obtaining their consent for data collection.

- Recruitment and information

Recruitment forms: WP6 partners have the option of recruiting from the focus groups established for WP5 and/or through a call published on their website and with the help of their local partners (members of the support group and other stakeholders) or they can also recruit the participants through an agency.

In any case, WP6 partners should issue a letter of invitation or launch a call with information on the purpose of the CP, its context (local and MeDeMAP research project) and its organization (venue and dates). The call should emphasize the benefits for participants (a participatory experience in policymaking, co-creating resolutions on the future of media and democracy, meeting and learning from experts, and the benefits of allowances).

- Call online: COMMIT and MI have set up an application form online (see [COMMIT Application form](#), [MI Application form](#)). CU and MIC have created a webpage promoting the call (see CU [webpage](#), MIC [webpage](#)), while applications should be addressed to their teams by mail. In all cases, a team member acknowledges applications and informs the applicants about the next step, as applicants will be asked to complete a selection questionnaire.

- FAQ: A Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) on the website provides an opportunity to present important information concisely. See for example COMMIT (in German) <https://medemap.commit.at/faq/> and CU <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/faq/>

- Selection

The selection process must be transparent and accountable to meet the transparency quality criterion (OECD, 2020, p. 118).

The Grant Agreement stipulates (p. 12) that “*the sociodemographic composition of the citizens’ parliaments should be guided by the idea of a kind of “audience council” representing the interest of readers, listeners, viewers and online media users across various sociodemographic groups.*”

WP6 partners will aim at socio-demographic diversity and diversity of perspectives. The selection criteria will be similar to those of the focus groups defined by IULM for WP5 (Miconi, Ferri, et al., 2024, pp. 11-13). Besides, participants should not know each other and should not have a function in a political party or work as journalists.

Each WP6 partner will develop a questionnaire for its CP candidates (or review the questionnaire with the recruiting agency), with questions relating to sociodemographic characteristics and opinions on media and politics, in order to balance the composition of the panel.

Selection of participants will be based on the replies to the questionnaire compared to the defined criteria. If needed, a new call might be advised to complete the panel of participants (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2025, 3 January).

Selection bias: Past experiences of CPs have shown that, whatever the selection processes, the final cast will include people who are more interested in the subject than the average population. This is difficult to avoid. In this case, it is all the more important that the facilitator ensures that people with different perspectives feel valued and encouraged to attend all sessions of the CP (Deliverable D6.1 – Monnot et al. 2024, p.55).

Annex 1 contains the applicant questionnaires developed by COMMIT (in German), CU and MIC.

- List of participants and consents

NewDemocracy (2019, p. 149) recommends contacting selected participants individually. Inviting them to a presentation or meeting them in person would make it possible to establish a more personal relationship and obtain their consent for data collection. (This can also help to establish a budget for possible travel costs or other expenses).

- COMMIT plans to organize two information meetings for selected participants (including the reserve list), one face to face and one online.
- CU is calling preselected applicants.
- Remuneration of participants/compensation.

Statistics on CPs show that remuneration varies widely from country to country and from CP to CP. The OECD Good Practice Principles (OECD 2020, pp. 94-95) recommend granting

indemnity, but some institutions, such as the Vorarlberg Civic Participation Office (FEB), consider participation to be a civic duty and do not provide compensation.

How much should Assembly Members be paid? "*The amount depends on the context,*" conclude the guidelines of DemocracyNext (2025, 3 January). Examples given range from US\$20 in Brazil to US\$160 in the US.

WP6 partners will provide compensation in line with local practices and regulations.

- Respect for privacy and consent to data collection

To be recruited, applicants should agree to group photos and voice recordings during plenary sessions. WP6 partners will decide if their names will be published on the website.

Photos will be group photos (no close-ups). There will be no video recording. The audio recording will cover the plenary discussions during the deliberation and adoption phases.

Consent forms for participants

It is recommended to explicitly inform the participants about the necessity to sign a consent form framing the use of their data and the respect for privacy, as their agreement is a condition for participation. These consent forms are necessary for data collection and analysis. Blank consent forms will be uploaded to the CP platform before the start of CP1. Final versions of the consent forms will be ready for signature at the beginning of CP1.

WP6 partners, in accordance with local legislation and their respective constraints, will develop their own consent forms. The blank consent forms shall be uploaded to the CP platform by WP6 partners before CP1. Signed consent forms will be stored by the WP6 partners.

1.4 Support group/Advisory board

Some larger citizen assemblies have two boards, one to oversee the process and another to monitor the learning phase and the selection of experts. In the MeDeMAP project, the Support group, defined in the Methodological guidelines (pp. 13-14) as a body representing civil society, will assist in both functions and provide support according to the capacities of the individual members with the following tasks:

- networking with decision-makers and other stakeholders;
- communicating about the CP and disseminating the results;
- helping in the recruitment of participants and experts;
- providing financial, personal or material support (venue, catering, volunteers, access to communication services);
- helping to organize the national presentation of the results of the CP, i.e. liaising with government departments or relevant stakeholders.

Guidebooks on CPs recommend transparency about the members of the support group as a means of enhancing legitimacy, for example by listing their names and the name of their organization on the website.

1.5 Identification and selection of experts

The expert briefing is described in section 2.1 (Learning phase).

Experts should be identified and invited before mid-February and briefed at least three weeks before their input. CP organizers interviewed for the D6.1 report emphasize the benefit of testing their presentation before the event.

1.6 Venue, dates and logistics

- Dates

The General Agreement foresees that the implementation of the CPs will take place between M23 and M30 of the project (between February and August 2025).

The OECD Good Practice Principles recommend a minimum of 4 days “*to meaningfully deliberate and find common ground without feeling pushed toward a pre-ordained outcome*” (OECD, 2020, p. 119). Based on their experience, organizers and guidebook authors recommend weekends without public holidays for CP meetings. The intervals between the meetings should not be too short, so that participants have time for reflection, and not too long, so participants do not forget too much (Krenzer & Socher, 2024, p. 60). In practice, the organizers recommend a break of one to two weeks between meetings, depending on the local calendar. With this in mind, the WP6 partners have set the following dates for the 4 CP sessions in the respective countries:

Country	Place	CP1	CP2	CP3	CP4
Austria	Vienna	22.3	5.4	26.4	17.5
Czech Republic	different towns	15.3	5.4	26.4	17.5
Ireland	Limerick	22.3	5.4	26.4	10.5
Slovenia	Ljubljana	15.3	29.3	12.4	10.5

- Venue

According to the interviews conducted and to the guidebooks, the most important criteria concerning the venue are:

- Accessibility: The venues should be reachable by public transport and accessible to those with mobility challenges.
- Large bright room with good acoustics: The event room must be large enough to accommodate different forms of deliberation in plenary and small groups and have appropriate lighting (Krenzer & Socher, 2024, p. 105). The facilitators interviewed favored a single large room where participants could break into small groups but stay together (also easier for the facilitation team to manage). The acoustics should be good enough, both for the participants as well as for the audio recordings.

- Sufficient feel-good adornment and catering. Facilitators emphasize the importance of the "beauty" of space. Adequate catering and a coffee corner near the main room can help to make participants feel more comfortable.
- A complete moderation kit with flip charts, cards to fill, etc.
- Tables and chairs that are easy to push aside.
- Electronic equipment (PC, beamer, screen, microphones) and working connections for the presentations.

Symbolic aspects also play a role, e.g. concerning the location or the group photos documenting the CPs. The venue should be appropriate for this purpose. (Krenzer & Socher, 2024, p. 105).

1.7 Communication with the participants and external communication before the CPs

Communication serves to disseminate information to CP participants, stakeholders and the wider public and also ensures greater transparency.

Guidelines for blog posts are developed in section 2.3.

Deliverable 6.1 recommended that a dedicated website be set up on the partners' websites with information about the CP, the call and a FAQ. Such a webpage "*validates the assembly's existence in the public's eye, gives it a tangible trail, and serves a functional purpose as a communication platform.*" (Nowak, 2021, October 20).

Other possibilities for communication include press releases, interviews, announcements on various social networks, etc. For some examples see Annex 13. Partnerships with the media and/or NGOs should also be considered.

WP6 partners should keep track of external communication (social media posts, press releases, media articles). For example, with details of the date and communication tool:

WP6 Partner	Date	What	Where	Comment	Link
COMMIT	19.12.24	Press release on CP	OTS APA Science		https://www.ots.at/presseaussendung/OTS_20241219_OTS0128/demokratie-braucht-starke-medien-buergerinnen-bringen-ihre-perspektiven-ein

Guidebooks like those from the US-based platform GoVocal specialized in supporting participatory processes recommend the following communication techniques:

- Set up a digital platform
- Promote the CP with partners
- Push the CP on social media
- Issue a press release
- Send a newsletter or print media to your community

With regard to the content disseminated on the website or blog, Buergererrat.net (2020), the platform of the Vorarlberg region, advises presenting the purpose of the CP and its timetable, and also developing media graphics on some content for the learning phase.

Inviting journalists is a recurring dilemma for CP organizers, as they often demand access to the discussions and to the participants, thus breaking through the “safe space” necessary for deliberation. Therefore, learning from the CP organizers interviewed, D6.1 recommends making documents available to the media, but only inviting them to the opening and closing sessions. Having representatives on advisory boards such as MIC is another way of involving the media.

- Partners websites and social media for disseminating information on the CPs

COMMIT

- MeDeMAP CP-Blog & Info on CP in Austria: <https://medemap.commit.at/>
- Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/commit-at.bsky.social>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/communitymedieninstitut>
- Mastodon: https://mastodon.social/@COMMIT_at

CU

- Website subpage: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/>

MIC

- Website subpage: <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=0>

MI

- Website subpage: <https://www.mirovni-institut.si/mediji-demokracija/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/mirovni.institut.si/>
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/mirovni_institut/

1.8 The CP Platform and what CP participants will access

OEAW will set up a common digital platform by the end of February, called the “CP Platform”, with two main purposes. It will serve as an interface for CP participants to access information, express their agreement/dissent and feedback and complete the surveys, and it will store some of the data collected by the partners during the CPs (see Part 3 on data collection).

The CP Platform allows the participants to interact in the process and thus meets the requirements of a PAR approach as outlined by Carpentier & Wimmer (2024a)

- by expressing once more their approval or dissent of the resolutions between the CP sessions
 - by participating in the evaluation of the process with the survey after each CP
- Annex 7 and Annex 8 show the structure of the CP Platform and how to access the CP Platform, respectively.

The main landing page will only be accessible for the organizing WP6 partners, CP participants will access their national landing page in their national language after registration.

On their national landing page, CP participants will find:

- Before the CPs start, MeDeMAP information material including the training videos,
- After the CPs, the following documentation material:

- After CP1 only: the three PDF lists of subtopics uploaded by the national team
- The minutes of the CP
- A selection of photos
- After each CP, an interactive survey to fill in about their experience of the CP
- After CP2, CP3 and CP4: The adopted resolutions are uploaded by the national teams. Participants will have access to a text box (max. 500 words) for comments where they can express their confirmatory/dissenting opinions.

1.9 Tasks to achieve before the start of the CPs

Suggested time frame before start of CP	Who	Type of activity	Tasks
Sept-Nov. 2024	WP6 Partners	Support group	Constitute a Support group/Advisory board
Nov. 2024-Jan. 2025	WP6 Partners	Facilitation	Identification of facilitators
Dec. 2024-Jan. 2025	WP6 Partners	Call for participants/communication	Issue call (on web, flyer, disseminated by partners)
Jan.-Feb. 2025	WP6 Partners	Organization	Book venue
Jan.-Feb. 2025	WP6 Partners	Research & Analysis	Identification of observers
2 months	WP6 Partners	Communication	CP Information (FAQ) on partners' websites (links in D6.2) or CP information on flyer
4 weeks	WP6 Partners	Participants/Research	National consent forms finalized
Before CP	WP6 Partners	Organization	Define roles of each team members
shortly after the end of the call	WP6 Partners	Recruitment of participants	Questionnaire sent to participants
shortly after the end of the call	WP6 Partners	Recruitment of participants	Selection of participants (20 + 5 reserve list)
1 month before CP day	WP6 Partners	Learning phase	Recruitment of experts completed
25.02.2025	CU/ WP6 Partners	Research & Analysis	Observers' training (CU)
End February	COMMIT/CU	Learning phase	MeDeMAP learning videos available with subtitles
End February	OEAW	Participants/Research	CP Platform for data collection and for information & approval/dissent of CP-participants will be ready
3 weeks before input	WP6 Partners	Learning phase	Experts briefed on format and content of presentation
3 weeks	WP6 Partners	Organization	Final check for venue if any aspect has been left open (room, facilitation kit, electronic material, recording material, catering, etc.)

2 weeks	WP6 Partners	Recruitment of participants	Individual calls or meetings of/with selected participants (COMMIT info meetings face to face 3.3, online 10.3)
2 weeks	WP6 Partners	Communication/Blog	First blog post (post in English for WP6 blog curated by COMMIT / WP6 partners on own blog or social media in local language)
2 weeks	WP6 Partners	Participants/ Research	Prepare national page for CP Platform
After CP1 (15.3 or 22.3)	WP6 Partners	Organization	List of participants on CP Platform. Consent forms collected.

Remarks

- Consent Forms: It is recommended to already communicate the criteria for consent with CP applicants when sending out the selection questionnaire. The final versions of the consent forms will be ready for signature at the beginning of CP1.
- Training videos: COMMIT will make the three training videos (Media Systems, Media Representation and Media Participation) available as part of the learning material on the CP platform and on the Austrian community TV "DORFTV" for communication to a wider public. The videos will remain online for the duration of the project.

2 CP implementation

COMMIT and CU have designed detailed scripts shown in Annexes 4 and 5, which can be used as models. The common CP design follows mandatory sequences with common mandatory elements described in 2.1.1.

- **Summary of the 4 days sessions** (CP walkthrough, extract from the Methodological Guidelines, October 2024)

Day 1	<p>Arrival and get-together</p> <p>Host welcome, check-in, overview of the CP's process</p> <p>Participants agree on CP objectives & procedures, and establish discussion rules</p> <p>Learning phase: Introduction to the main theme and the 3 topics, Q&A session.</p> <p>Discussion on the sub-topics for each of the three topics (output: three lists of sub-topics).</p> <p>Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings</p>
Day 2	<p>Arrival and get-together.</p> <p>Learning phase: topic 1 (Media systems)</p> <p>Confirming list of sub-topics for topic 1 (or modifying it)</p> <p>Deliberation: Discussion & development of proposals</p> <p>Decision-making: Voting on the resolutions/recommendations</p> <p>Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings</p>
After Day 2	<p>Creation of Minutes, with all resolutions</p> <p>Online opportunity for dissenting opinions</p>
Day 3	<p>Arrival and get-together.</p> <p>Learning phase: topic 2 (Participation in the media)</p> <p>Confirming list of sub-topics for topic 2 (or modifying it)</p> <p>Deliberation: Discussion & development of proposals</p> <p>Decision-making: Voting on the resolutions/recommendations</p> <p>Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings</p>
After Day 3	<p>Creation of Minutes, with all resolutions/recommendations</p> <p>Online opportunity for dissenting opinions</p>
Day 4	<p>Arrival and get-together</p> <p>Learning phase: topic 3 (Representation in the media)</p> <p>Confirming list of sub-topics for topic 3 (or modifying it)</p> <p>Deliberation: Discussion & development of proposals</p> <p>Decision-making: Voting on the recommendations/resolutions</p> <p>Face-to-face opportunity for dissenting opinions</p> <p>CP wrap up and conclusion</p>
National event (June 2025)	<p>Presentation of resolutions/recommendations to media and political stakeholders and to the broader public</p>
European event (January or February 2026)	<p>Presentations as part of WP7 dissemination in Brussels (participation of 2 citizens per national CP)</p>

2.1 Framework for the CP script

2.1.1 CP Script: mandatory components

Both the COMMIT and the CU CP scripts (Annexes 4 and 5) serve as models to be adapted, but WP6 partners are expected to follow the following mandatory steps:

- Check in and check out with the participants at the beginning and end of each CP session
- At the end of the day: Indications for participants for the next CP session (documentation available, expression of approval/dissent, short feedback survey on CP platform). Availability of the team to help access CP platform.
- The experts have been briefed on the learning outcomes, on the audience and on the input format and have received the links to the videos. The role of an expert can also be fulfilled by an expert member of the national team.

Day 1:

- Agreeing on the CP's objectives, procedures and discussion rules
- Learning stage with experts' inputs: The theme "Media and Democracy" will be presented according to the learning objectives, as a basis for the participants' deliberations. The inputs are followed by Q&A or a deliberation session where experts are available.
Two options: presentation of the videos and one or two expert presentations OR the team make sure participants have watched the videos before the CP. In that case, the experts and the team can answer questions related to the videos' content.
- Outcome of CP1: Establishment of a preliminary topic list for the three topics.

Day 2, 3 and 4:

- CP days order: The order of processing the topic "representation in the media" and "participation in and through the media" on Day 3 or Day 4 might differ. COMMIT will have "participation in and through the media" on Day 3. CU and MIC will have this topic covered on Day 4.
- Learning stage with experts' inputs (and one video), followed by Q&A and/or deliberation session on inputs where experts are available.

Establishment of final subtopic list:

- Refinement of sub-topic list of the day (suppression, addition, refinement). (Small groups, topic café with several rounds)
- Adoption of refined list in plenary
- Prioritization of topics of final list (i.e. dot-voting)

Draft and adoption of resolutions:

- Participants are divided into small groups to develop resolutions on clustered sub-topics (action café, rotation tables with 3-5 rounds, see scripts) with support from the moderators for drafting

- Presentation of resolutions for confirmation/veto/amendment
- Adoption of resolution

Day 4: same sequences as Day 2 and Day 3 with additional closure sequence and “celebration”

- CP wrap up, information regarding the presentation of results before checking out.
- Celebration

For further details, refer to the COMMIT and CU CP scripts in Annexes 4 and 5, respectively.

2.1.2 Activities between and after the CP sessions

Activities between CP1 and CP2					
Activities	Start	End	Description	Material outcomes	Tech./Mat. Needs
Blog post 2	After CP session 1		Post in English for WP6 blog curated by COMMIT/on own blogs or social media in local language	Blog post to disseminate on social media	COMMIT WP6 blog and EPALE
Minutes of CP1	After CP1	Uploaded 1 week after CP1	Brief factual minutes of CP process by national teams (focus on 3 subtopics list)	Minutes uploaded on CP Platform	CP Platform
Short feedback survey	After CP1	Published together with the minutes	A very short survey online for the CP participants, about the experiences of CP1	Survey answers	Survey form part of CP Platform
Subtopics cleaning proposal	After minutes are uploaded	Before CP2	MeDeMAP national team analyses the subtopics and respectfully enhances quality, uploads it, and informs CP participants to read it	Improved three lists of subtopics (to be refined in next CP sessions)	CP Platform

Activities after CP2, CP3 and CP4					
Activities	Start	End	Description	Material outcomes	Tech./Mat. Needs
Blog posts 3, 4, 5	After CP session 2, 3 and 4		Posts in English for WP6 blog curated by COMMIT/on own blogs or social media in local language	Blog post to disseminate on social media	COMMIT WP6 blog and EPALE
Minutes of last CP	After last CP	Uploaded 1 week after last CP	Brief factual minutes of CP process by national teams (focus on 3 subtopics list)	Minutes uploaded on CP Platform	CP Platform

Resolutions uploaded	After last CP	Uploaded 1 week after last CP	Each resolution is uploaded separately on confirmatory/dissenting section of the platform	Resolutions separately uploaded on platform	Resolution response on CP Platform
Invitation to participants to express confirmatory/dissenting opinions	One week after last CP	Before next CP	Participants are invited to express confirmation or dissent with resolutions on the platform. MeDeMAP team to assist.	New opportunity for participants to reflect on topic and results	Resolution response on CP Platform
Short feedback survey	After last CP	together with the minutes	A very short survey for the CP participants, about the experiences of last CP	Survey answers	Survey question part of CP Platform

2.1.3 Guiding questions for the four CP sessions

The Art of Hosting method, which will be used for facilitation, recommends framing the main theme of a CP in the form of a question (called the "calling question"). This question embodies the purpose of the meeting and invites people to explore solutions together (Corrigan, 2009, p. 26).

The Dutch foundation DemocracyNext (2023), which is committed to promoting citizens' parliaments, advises the following when framing the questions:

- Think about what decisions the Assembly can influence to help solve the problem(s)
- Involve stakeholders in defining the question
- Find the balance between a frame that is too broad to result in useful recommendations and too narrow to miss a chance to generate new and helpful ideas

For its part, Citizenlab (2022, p. 12), a platform specialized in assisting the organization of CPs, recommends breaking down the topic to allow for a "brainstorming about concrete measurable solutions" and suggest formulations such as "what could be done on the side of ... to improve...".

Based on the MeDeMAP Learning objectives (see Annex 2) and on the questions addressed to media representatives in MeDeMAP Deliverable 4.3 on media production from the angle of political participation (Klimkiewicz, 2025), the following questions could be used to introduce the topics of each session:

- CP1 Media and Democracy: How can media best serve democracy? What are the most important roles the media should play?
- CP2 Media system & Media regulation: What characteristics must the media system have to best support democracy? What are the threats? What kind of regulation can help the media system support democracy?
- CP3/4 Participation in and through media: How can greater participation in the media support democracy? What can more participation in the media look like?

- How can participation through the media facilitate political participation/support democracy?
- CP4/3 Representation in the media: What are the conditions that support cultural/societal and political diversity in news coverage?

2.2 Facilitation

The purpose of this section is to review the role of facilitation and to present some techniques and tools from the Art of Hosting that can be used during CPs following the model scripts.

2.2.1 Role of facilitation

As noted in Report D6.1, a high-quality deliberative process prevails when

- Facilitation ensures respect, mutual understanding, and equal access to expression,
- Co-creation of solutions is achieved in small group and panel discussions.

According to Krenzer & Socher (2024, p. 22), the role of facilitation is to ensure that

- All participants have their say and express their points of view.
- There is a pleasant, protected atmosphere and rules of discussion are followed.
- Communication is respectful and at eye level.
- The exchange is structured and leads to a result.

Hence, facilitators must support respectful interactions, make sure all have equal chances to speak, and that any judgments made are based on evidence and careful deliberation (DemocracyNext, accessed 2025, January 3).

- A participatory action research (PAR) approach

Adopting a PAR approach in the CPs means that CP participants go through a circular process of learning, reflecting on that learning, developing solutions, and reflecting again in an iterative co-creation process, as expressed in Deliverable 2.2 for Work Package 2 (Carpentier & Wimmer, 2024a, p. 35).

To ensure a PAR approach, WP6 partners have agreed that iteratively

- CP members determine how many resolutions (approximately) the CP intends to make and set the rules for deliberation and adoption (agreement on the CP's objectives, procedures and discussion rules on Day 1)

Based on what

- CP members decide which sub-topics to prioritize before deliberating and adopting resolutions

After adopting resolutions after deliberation during the CP session

- CP members will get the opportunity to express again approval or dissent or to give any feedback after the CP sessions on Day 1, Day 2 and Day 3 (online form on CP Platform)
- And CP members will be involved in the research process through online surveys after the CP sessions, interviews conducted with a selection of participants (after the end of

the CP) and through a group feedback analysis after the production of the national reports.

2.2.2 Recommendations collected from guidebooks on the organization of CPs

This section summarizes some recommendations from various guidebooks. Further references and resources on facilitation can be found in the References in section 4.

- Introduction to purpose and walkthrough of the CP

Usually, it is the role of the commissioner to welcome the CP members, and elicit the purpose of the CP, its expected outcomes, and what will be done with them. The facilitators introduce the agenda and often start with an icebreaker to get members to know each other (DemocracyNext, 2025, January 3).

- Agreement on the CP's objectives, procedures and discussion rules

This can be introduced with questions like

- What do we need to do to ensure we feel comfortable in our discussions? How can we support each other when this is not happening?
- Drafting recommendations and voting: Criteria must be defined to help the facilitator manage time when it is difficult to reach consensus. *"How can we manage to keep the discussion within the available time and come to results/resolutions at the end of each day?"*
- Drafting recommendations: Keep them short, aim at clarity and have the last version endorsed in plenary

"Once the group has feedback, they can revisit their recommendations and make any changes. You should remind them that they do not need to write long and complex recommendations, their focus is on clarity of intent. It's good practice to ensure you are continuing to mix the small writing groups so that the final words are owned by everyone rather than just a passionate small subset of the group." (NewDemocracy/UN, p. 193)

"Rewritten recommendations will need to be reviewed by the whole group to ensure their original intent has not been lost in the rewrite. This can be as simple as printing the recommendation and having them posted for feedback around the room." (NewDemocracy/UN, p. 193)

- Closing the CPs

Facilitator: Allow reflecting on the process (each say a few words in a circle). *"This is often a nice affirmation of the integrity of the process"* reminds NewDemocracy/UN (p. 198)

WP6 Partner: Wrap up the outcomes and inform about the follow-up: what will be done with the results, how they will be presented.

Let CP members decide who will present the results at the national presentation. NewDemocracy/UN (p. 199) recommends that *"Presentation to decision maker by participants The group should decide themselves who they think should present the final report. At most 3*

participants should give a quick speech re-capping the process and telling the story to decision makers. This is a powerful aspect of the process because it is a chance for everyday people to speak directly to decision makers on a topic that they have spent a lot of time learning and deliberating on. It conveys the ability of everyday people and gives additional weight to the recommendations in the report. “

Annex 6 presents facilitation tools and references that could be used for CPs.

2.3 The learning phase

The learning phase aims to enable CP members to make an informed judgment before drafting and adopting resolutions.

In large citizens' assemblies convened by public authorities, the number of experts is usually high and includes a mix of government speakers, independent experts, civil society representatives, and practitioners (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023, p. 9).

As stated in report D6.1, the diversity of perspectives and completeness are the most important quality criteria concerning the content of the inputs.

The learning phase in the CPs will be followed by a reflection on the learning before the participants prioritize the topics to be dealt with. The learning inputs will include training videos and expert interventions. One expert intervention will provide a broader overview of the issues at stake and a second expert intervention will provide a case study or examples. In the latter case, the expert can decide which type of media to address, but CP organizers should avoid that all case studies/examples are about one type of media.

As it might be difficult to find practitioners with a good overview of the whole media landscape, this may lead to asking academics to present case studies. In practice, the choice will be restricted by the availability of experts.

Transparency is another aspect advocated by the OECD (2020, pp. 118-119). Some learning documents should be promoted not only on the CP platform, which is only accessible to participants, but also on the national websites of the partners.

The following documents will be available for participants on the CP platform:

- MeDeMAP training videos on Media Systems, Media Representation and Media Participation on CP platform (also on the Austrian community TV “Dorf TV”);
- Information materials prepared by the national teams (on their section of the CP platform);
- A selection of relevant publications as background material.

2.3.1 Learning objectives

The Learning objectives developed by CU and COMMIT are presented in Annex 2. This document has provided the common thread for the training videos. It also serves as guidelines for the briefing of the two experts on the expected learning outcomes.

2.3.2 Training videos

The three MeDeMAP training videos, produced by CU and COMMIT with support from Lusofona and featuring interviews with WP leaders and team members from CU, JU and IULM, each present in about ten minutes the main learning points related to media systems, media representation and participation in and through media. They were guided by the learning objectives.

The scripts and production were developed by CU and COMMIT. The WP6 partners all contributed to the translation of the subtitles into their own languages. The videos will be published by COMMIT on the CP platform and will also be available on the Austrian community TV "Dorf TV".

These videos serve not only as learning material for CP participants, but also as reference material for experts. Another reference for experts is *Democracy and Media in Europe* by Carpentier & Wimmer (2024b), published as Open Access.

2.3.3 Expert briefing

Concerning the experts' presentations, the main recommendations gathered from interviews with CP organizers and CP facilitators for D6.1 and from guidebooks are:

- Experts should have didactic skills; their contributions should be short and clearly formulated so that they can be understood by everyone (Handler, 2024);
- CP members should be asked if they feel there are any gaps in the information (DemocracyNext, 2025 January 3);
- Experts should be available for Q&A sessions (OECD, 2020, p. 37; Ingruber, 2024 and Handler, 2024);
- Information packages should be accessible and include different types of documents like text, videos, podcasts or graphics (Handler, 2024).

The expert briefing guidelines (Annex 3) aim to inform experts about the audience of the CP and the expected format of their contributions.

2.4 Communication and dissemination of CP national implementation and results, including D6.3 - Blog on CPs (M25-30)

2.4.1 Blog and guidelines for blog posts

COMMIT has set up a CP blog <https://medemap.commit.at/> that both communicates the national Austrian CP and has a subsection in English dedicated to the CPs of the MeDeMAP partners to publish the contributions of the WP6 partners as part of the third deliverable of WP6 (D6.3), see: <https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>.

WP6 partners will each draft and provide at least 6 blog posts in English (max. 3000 characters, including one or two photos with credits), one before the start of the CPs, one after each session and one after the national presentation. WP6 Partners will send their blog posts by mail to medemap@commit.at. Annex 9 provides guidelines for writing blog posts.

Partners may decide to create their own blog to inform and disseminate at national level in their local language.

COMMIT will publish articles and blog posts also on EPALE, the European adult learning platform. WP6 partners are invited also to open accounts on EPALE and to share and support the EPALE posts with comments.

2.4.2 Dissemination at the national level

Sensibilization of the public as an aspect of dissemination started already in November 2025 with the national calls to apply for participation in the Citizen Parliaments. This has been achieved so far via websites, posters or flyers but also by the use of social media platforms and newsletters by all partners. As an example for very large reach out might be seen the call for participation in Austria published in Vienna's quarterly paper "Mein Wien" - with a circulation of 1.3 million copies, this magazine reaches every household in Vienna (see Annex13).

CP resolutions and other outcomes of the CPs will be compiled in a "CP Results" document to be presented to relevant stakeholders at the national level by all WP6. A special role will play here the national events in June 2025, where the CP results will be presented and discussed with members of the citizen parliaments. Each partner will also use this event for presence on social media platforms and to reach out to stakeholders and a broad public.

Each partner is responsible for setting up its detailed outreach plan and is encouraged to identify the best ways to reach out to decision-makers and interested groups to maximize the impact of CP decisions and outcomes. Potential stakeholders to be addressed are among others:

- representatives of political parties – responsible for media and fundamental rights policy
- media regulation authorities
- representative organizations from the media industry including public service, commercial and non-commercial sector
- Press and/or Media Councils
- journalist unions
- professional representatives of consumers and chambers of commerce
- national UNESCO committees
- NGOs active in the field of social justice, support for minority groups, Human Rights and Media Freedom
- academic institutions active in the field of social science and media economy
- adult education providers active in the field of Media Literacy

Some of the stakeholders mentioned are already involved in the advisory councils which have been set up for each country. A supplementary way for dissemination might be the presence as speaker or panellist at cultural and educational events.

Before the production of the national reports (see Data Analysis, section 3.3), the WP6 partners will present a preliminary analysis of their results at the public panel organized by COMMIT during the final project meeting in Vienna (24-26.09.2025).

2.4.3 Presentation of the results in Brussels

The CPs' outcomes will be presented to representatives of the EU Commission and to members of the European Parliament at the occasion of the European event organized by WP7 leader in Brussels in January or February 2026. Citizen parliaments will be represented by two CP participants from each country. Each WP6 partner will identify Members of the European Parliament and other potential stakeholders who could be interested in supporting this final event at the European Parliament in Brussels.

COMMIT will coordinate the communication of results towards specific European and international organizations which should include among others:

- UNESCO's Communication and Information Sector
- Members of the European Parliaments with a focus on the committee for culture and education (CULT), the committee on civil liberties, justice and home affairs (LIBE) and the committee on Human Rights (DROI).
- The European Commission
- The Fundamental Rights Agency in Vienna
- The OSCE Representative on Freedom of the Media in Vienna
- European Regulators Group for Audiovisual Media Services (ERGA)
- European Platform of Regulatory Authorities (EPRA) and its working group on Media and Information Literacy (EMIL)
- Steering Committee on Media and Information Society (CDMSI) at the Council of Europe
- European representative organizations of media and journalists: EBU, EFJ, CMFE, RSF.
- European Association for the Education of Adults (EAEA).

2.4.4 Dissemination of the results in academic and non-academic publications

WP6 partners are encouraged to identify academic and/or non-academic publications to disseminate the results of the CPs. COMMIT will support with suggestions from the field of adult education and community media. This includes the presence in community radio and TV shows - if available in the relevant areas - but also in trade press outlets. As an example, we mention for Austria the national adult education quarterly "Die Österreichische Volkshochschule" which will publish an article provided by COMMIT in its 4/2025 issue. A detailed plan for academic publications will be developed by OEAW starting with the project meeting in Prague in March 2025.

3 Data collection and analysis

Data collection during the CPs and its further analysis by WP6 and WP2 will allow to fulfil the following two research tasks:

- Task 6.3: Analysis of the sessions and final decisions of citizens' parliaments, with a focus on the content/output of the recommendations and of the process to generate that content. (Deliverable 6.4)
- Task 6.4: Evaluation of PAR research, with a focus on the analysis of the participatory process & the construction of media and democracy, incorporated into the theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions (Deliverable 2.4)

The WP6 partners are responsible for collecting, selecting and analysing the data in their national CP and for writing up a national report on the basis of this analysis. An overview of the data to be collected, the methodological approaches used, the analysis and the main outcomes is given in Annex 11. The research coordination from OEAW in cooperation with COMMIT will be responsible for finalizing the research design, developing methodological protocols and templates, offering training to the WP6 partners and organizing the synchronization of the qualitative analysis by WP6 partners. The two ethnographic observers from each CP will be trained by CU in February.

The national reports form the basis for the aggregated analysis of the CPs for Deliverables 6.4 (Report "Future roadmap for European media and democracy", by COMMIT) and 2.4 ("Theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions", by CU).

3.1 Research questions

The two main research questions connected to the two WP6 research tasks (6.3 and 6.4) are:

- Task 6.3: How do the citizen parliaments in the four countries envision the democratic roles of media in their recommendations for future perspectives and in the processes leading to these recommendations?
- Task 6.4: How are democracy and media constructed in the participatory process of the four CPs?

Each research question is split into several secondary research questions. They can be found in detail in Annex 10. The research questions build on the theoretical framework laid out in Deliverable 2.1 (Carpentier & Wimmer 2024b). Annex 12 (indications for the CP observers' training) provides useful guidelines for unpacking the research questions and linking them to the relevant sections in the theoretical framework.

3.2 Data collection

To answer the two research questions, a variety of data is collected during, between and after the CPs (see Annex 11):

- the final resolutions/recommendations adopted on each of the 3 topics (with votes and expressions of confirmation or dissent),
- minutes of the CP sessions,

- flipcharts and posters produced during the CP sessions
- audio recordings and selective transcripts of plenary discussions (no video recording),
- field notes (from ethnographic observers)
- online surveys after each CP
- interviews with a selection of participants (after the end of the CPs)

Some of these data will be uploaded to the CP platform for participants to access (adopted resolutions, CP minutes and selected photos). Some data will be gathered through the CP platform itself (votes and expressions of confirmatory/dissenting opinions to the resolutions, online survey). All other collected data will be stored and managed by the partners nationally (audio recordings and selective transcripts of plenary discussions and interviews, field notes).

All data will be collected in the national language of the CP. The CP minutes and resolutions and selected passages/quotes from the audio recordings and other data to be included in the national reports will be translated into English by the partners. As participants will get the opportunity to comment on the results of the analysis (group feedback analysis, see 3.3.2), it will be important to be able to present results both in English and in the national language.

3.2.1 Minutes of the CP sessions including resolutions and photos

The minutes of each CP session should be short and list the main activities done (following the structure of the prepared CP script, i.e. learning stage, group and plenary discussions) and the outcomes (established topic lists and adopted resolutions). They will be uploaded to the CP Platform for the participants and for data analysis but won't be published.

The minutes are complemented by a photo protocol of all flipcharts and posters produced during the CP sessions. The CP minutes and (selected) photos are uploaded to the CP platform one week after each session for the CP participants (see section 2.1.2).

For analysis, the adopted resolutions will be complemented by the expressed confirmatory/dissenting opinions submitted on the CP platform.

3.2.2 Audio recording and transcription

During the CPs, plenary discussions connected to the establishment of subtopic lists and the adoption of resolutions will be audio recorded. The learning phase and group discussions will not be recorded. There will be no video recordings.

After the CPs, each WP6 partner is responsible for selecting relevant sections of the plenary discussions for transcription and further analysis. Guidelines for transcription will be developed by the research coordination. Transcription will not require identifying individual speakers and matching their statements, although observer notes can help with that if that is desired.

3.2.3 Ethnographic observation

The two observers of each CP will focus on compiling field notes for one of the main research questions respectively during the four sessions of the CPs. One question addresses the generation of the resolutions, the other the way democracy and media are constructed (see instructions for the observers' training in Annex 12).

Training: CU will organize training for the observers on February 25, 2025, with an introduction to ethnographic research and methods and guidelines for observing and taking notes.

3.2.4 Online surveys and interviews

After each CP, all participants are asked to fill out a short online survey on the CP Platform to give feedback on their experience of the day. The research coordination will draft the survey in English until the beginning of March and WP6 partners will translate it into their national languages to be put on the CP Platform before CP1.

After the last CP, short face-to-face-interviews with a selection of participants should be conducted and audio recorded. It is recommended to ask participants during or at the end of Day 4 to volunteer for these interviews. WP6 partners are free to decide how many interviews they want to conduct, but it is recommended to aim at five interviews to ensure that different perspectives are included. The interviews are expected to complement and deepen the insights from the online surveys.

3.3 Data analysis

3.3.1 Qualitative analysis and national reports

After the CP, each partner will analyse their national CP based on the data collected and write up a national report with these two main sections until 15.10.2025:

- analysis of the recommendations and of their development process (Task 6.3),
- analysis of the participatory process (Task 6.4)

The analysis of the collected data will be in the form of a qualitative textual and discourse analysis that will answer the research questions and provide contextualized quotes from the data.

OEAW will produce a methodological protocol for the qualitative textual/discourse analysis of the results of the citizens' parliaments including templates for the national reports and will organize an analytical training for WP6 partners.

The national reports will be compiled in an aggregated analysis of the CPs for Deliverables 6.4 (Report "Future roadmap for European media and democracy", by COMMIT) and 2.4 ("Theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions", by CU).

WP6 partners will present a preliminary analysis of their results at the public panel organized by COMMIT during the last project meeting in Vienna (24-26.09.2025).

3.3.2 Group feedback analysis

As a closing participatory research component of the PAR approach, a group feedback analysis (GFA) (Heller 1976) will be organized to give participants the opportunity to give feedback to the draft national reports before they go into the aggregated analysis for D6.4 and D2.4.

The research coordination will organize an analytical training for the group feedback analysis.

Conclusion

This deliverable serves to provide a framework for the design of the citizens' parliaments organized by the WP6 partners. The proposed design is inspired by the findings from the analysis of successful practices of citizens' parliaments (D6.1), the inclusion of a PAR approach (D2.2) and the prospect of data collection for the subsequent phases of the MeDeMAP project.

The CPs on Media and Democracy, which will take place between March and June 2025 in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia will bear the same design features, follow the same sequences, adopt a PAR approach and an identical facilitation method; they share the same learning objectives and aim at the same type of results. The CP organized online in Germany will also follow the same pattern.

However, even though they will be organized in synchrony by the WP6 partners, as with any social experience, the adventure of each CP will be a unique one. The local contexts are different. In some partner countries, citizen consultations are already a tradition, while others will play a pioneering role. Public acceptance and stakeholder involvement will also strongly depend on the political context and the respective attention to media and democracy. Local rules and customs will also have an impact on practical organization. Not to mention the participants themselves, who will give each parliament a unique dynamic.

For this reason, we have presented the common design features of the CPs and the steps to implement them, but detailed scripts or tools such as questionnaires are provided in the appendices as models that can be adapted.

However unique, the experience of the four face-to-face CPs where citizens learn, reflect, prioritize issues and develop and adopt resolutions will be observed and documented for the continuation of the MeDeMAP research project. The data gathered in the national reports of the WP6 partners will allow comparative data analysis for Deliverables D6.4 and D2.4.

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5 Annexes

Annex 1: Questionnaires for applicants – COMMIT, CU, MI

Annex 1a: COMMIT- -Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie – Fragebogen für Bewerber*innen

Wir freuen uns, dass Sie am Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie in Österreich teilnehmen wollen! Für den Bürger*innenrat wollen wir eine möglichst diverse Gruppe an Teilnehmenden zusammenstellen, die die Vielfalt der österreichischen Gesellschaft abbilden. Ihre Antworten auf den folgenden Fragebogen werden uns bei der Auswahl helfen.

Bitte beachten Sie, dass wir Ihre Bewerbung nur berücksichtigen können, wenn Sie den Fragebogen vollständig beantworten und am Ende abschicken. Die Informationen, die Sie in diesem Fragebogen zur Verfügung stellen, verwenden wir nur für die Auswahl von Teilnehmer*innen für den Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie. Wir verwenden sie nicht für andere Zwecke und geben sie nicht an Dritte weiter.

Der Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie wird von COMMIT – Community Medien Institut für Weiterbildung, Forschung und Beratung im Rahmen des europäischen Forschungsprojekts MeDeMAP organisiert. Weitere Informationen dazu finden Sie auf unserem Blog unter: <https://medemap.commit.at/>

Voraussetzungen für die Teilnahme am Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie

Bitte beachten Sie: Der Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie ist ein demokratisches Instrument, das Bürger*innen dabei unterstützen soll, Empfehlungen und Forderungen zu formulieren, die sich an die Politik und die Medien in Österreich richten. Daher können Sie nur teilnehmen, wenn Sie selbst keine politische Funktion in Österreich ausüben und Ihre Haupterwerbstätigkeit nicht im Medienbereich liegt (z.B. professionelle*r Journalist*in, Redakteur*in, Medienherausgeber*in). Aufgrund der Bedingungen des europäischen Forschungsprojekts müssen Sie für eine Teilnahme über 18 Jahre alt sein.

Wenn Sie zur Teilnahme am Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie ausgewählt werden, werden wir Sie darum bitten, eine Einverständniserklärung zu unterzeichnen, mit der Sie der Verwendung aller erhobenen Daten im Rahmen des Bürger*innenrats für die Zwecke der Forschung und Öffentlichkeitsarbeit im Projekt MeDeMAP zustimmen. Sie können diese Einverständniserklärung vorab hier einsehen:

<https://medemap.commit.at/einverstaendniserklaerung/>

Bei Rückfragen und Unklarheiten wenden Sie sich bitte an COMMIT unter medemap@commit.at.

Ich bestätige, dass ich die Voraussetzungen für eine Teilnahme am Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie erfülle.

1. Wie alt sind Sie?
 - 18-24 Jahre
 - 25-34 Jahre
 - 35-44 Jahre

45-54 Jahre
55-64 Jahre
Über 64 Jahre

2. Was ist Ihr Geschlecht?

männlich
weiblich
divers / anderes
Möchte ich nicht sagen

3. Was ist der höchste Bildungsabschluss, den Sie erreicht haben?

Grundschulabschluss
Mittelschule / Pflichtschulabschluss
Lehre mit Berufsschule / Fach- oder Handelsschule
Höhere Schule mit Matura (AHS/BHS)
Abschluss an einer Universität/Hochschule (Diplom/Bachelor/Master)
Doktorat
Anderer Abschluss (bitte beschreiben)

4. Wo haben Sie Ihren Hauptwohnsitz?

.....

5. Welche Staatsbürgerschaft haben Sie?

Österreichische Staatsbürgerschaft (seit der Geburt)
Österreichische Staatsbürgerschaft (später erworben)
Andere Staatsbürgerschaft:

6. Was ist derzeit Ihre Haupterwerbstätigkeit? (Sie können mehr als eine Option auswählen. Zum Beispiel: Selbstständig + In Ausbildung, usw.)

In Ausbildung (Schule, Lehre, Studium)
Angestellt
Selbstständig
Arbeitslos
Haushaltsführend
In Karenz
In Pension
Sonstige (bitte beschreiben) _____

7. Falls Sie erwerbstätig sind, was ist Ihre berufliche Tätigkeit? Falls Sie studieren, was ist Ihr Studienfach?

8. Wie interessiert sind Sie an den Nachrichten?

Sehr interessiert
Ziemlich interessiert
Nicht sehr interessiert
Überhaupt nicht interessiert

9. Wie viel Zeit verbringen Sie im Durchschnitt an einem normalen Tag mit dem Lesen, Schauen oder Hören von Nachrichten? (Es spielt keine Rolle, welches Medium Sie dafür benutzen)

Weniger als 10 Minuten
10-30 Minuten
mehr als 30 Minuten, aber weniger als 1 Stunde
1 Stunde oder mehr

10. Haben Sie in den letzten 5 Jahren an einer politischen Wahl teilgenommen (z. B. gewählt)?

Ja
Nein

11. Sind Sie Mitglied einer politischen Partei oder einer politischen Bewegung?

Ja
Nein

12. Sind Sie in einer anderen politisch engagierten Organisation erwerbsmäßig oder auf Freiwilligenbasis tätig (z. B. NGO, Organisation der Zivilgesellschaft, aktivistische Organisation)?

Ja
Nein

Wenn ja, in welcher Art von Organisation? (optional) _____

13. Haben Sie in den letzten 12 Monaten an Demonstrationen, Protesten oder Petitionen (auch online) teilgenommen?

Ja
Nein

Wie sehr stimmen Sie den folgenden Aussagen zu? Wählen Sie für jede Aussage eine Option aus.

14. Die Regierung sollte mehr Mittel investieren, um soziale und wirtschaftliche Ungleichheiten in der Gesellschaft abzubauen.

Stimme voll und ganz zu
Stimme eher zu
Neutral (stimme weder zu noch nicht zu)

Stimme eher nicht zu
Stimme nicht zu
Ich weiß es nicht

15. Die Migration von Menschen aus anderen Teilen der Welt ist eine Bereicherung für die österreichische Gesellschaft

Stimme voll und ganz zu
Stimme eher zu
Neutral (stimme weder zu noch nicht zu)
Stimme eher nicht zu
Stimme nicht zu
Ich weiß es nicht

16. Wie viel Vertrauen haben Sie in die folgenden Institutionen, dass sie eine positive Rolle in der Gesellschaft spielen? Wählen Sie für jede Institution (Regierung, Medien, Wissenschaft) eine Option aus.

- a. Regierung
- Vollkommenes Vertrauen
 - Einigermaßen Vertrauen
 - Neutral [weder Vertrauen noch Misstrauen]
 - Etwas Misstrauen
 - Völliges Misstrauen
- b. Medien
- Vollkommenes Vertrauen
 - Einigermaßen Vertrauen
 - Neutral [weder Vertrauen noch Misstrauen]
 - Etwas Misstrauen
 - Völliges Misstrauen
- c. Wissenschaft
- Vollkommenes Vertrauen
 - Einigermaßen Vertrauen
 - Neutral [weder Vertrauen noch Misstrauen]
 - Etwas Misstrauen
 - Völliges Misstrauen

Damit wir Ihre Antworten zuordnen können, bitte geben Sie Ihren Namen und Ihre E-Mail-Adresse an:

Name: _____
E-Mail: _____

Vielen Dank, dass Sie den Fragebogen ausgefüllt haben! Wir werden Sie ab Mitte Februar 2025 über die Auswahl an Teilnehmenden für den Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie informieren.

Annex 1b: CU - Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy – Survey questionnaire

We appreciate your interest in joining the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy! Filling out this questionnaire will help us to recruit participants for the citizen parliament.

Please note that you are expected to answer all questions (leaving questions unanswered will not allow you to complete and submit the filled-out questionnaire).

The organiser of the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy is CULCORC, the Culture and Communication Research Centre at the Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism at Charles University, as part of the European MeDeMAP research project.

You can find more information about the organisation of the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy here: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/>

1. What is your age?
 - Less than 18 y/o
 - 18-24 y/o
 - 25-35 y/o
 - 36-44 y/o
 - 45-54 y/o
 - 55-65 y/o
 - Over 65 y/o

2. What is your gender?
 - Man
 - Woman
 - Other
 - Prefer not to say

3. What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 - Elementary school
 - Middle school
 - High school
 - University/ Higher education
 - Master's degree
 - PhD
 - Other (please describe) _____

4. Where do you live? (city, town or village) (if you live in different places, please add the location where you spend most of your time)
.....

5. What is your current socio-professional status? (You can select more than one option. For example: Self-employed + student, etc.)
 - Employed
 - Self-employed
 - Unemployed
 - Student
 - House person

- On parental leave
- Retired
- Other (please describe) _____

6. If you are employed, what is your professional activity?

7. How interested are you in the news?

- Very interested
- Fairly interested
- Not very interested
- Not interested at all

8. How much time do you spend on average reading, watching or listening to the news on a typical day? (It doesn't matter which medium you use.)

- Less than 10 minutes
- 10-30 minutes
- more than 30 minutes, but less than 1 hour
- 1 hour or more

9. Have you participated in any political elections (e.g. voted) in the last 5 years?

- Yes
- No

10. Are you a member of any political party or political movement?

- Yes
- No

11. Are you engaged in the activities of any other organisation (e.g., NGO, civil society organisation, activist organisation)?

- Yes. If Yes, in what kind of organisation? _____
- No

12. Have you participated in demonstrations, protests, or petitions (including online) in the last 12 months?

- Yes
- No

How much do you agree with the following statements? Select one option for each statement.

13. Being Czech is the most important part of my identity.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

14. The migration of people from other parts of the world is enriching for the Czech society.

- Completely agree

- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

15. The world is already complicated enough, and it's better that we maintain our traditional values and our traditional family and gender roles.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

16. Each one of us should focus on taking care of our lives and defending our own interests; the other people's problems should not be our priority.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

17. We can overcome social problems, if we express solidarity to our fellow humans and help one another.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

18. Authorities and institutions have the responsibility to support our needs and help us solve our problems.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

19. We can trust other people to support our needs and help us solve our problems.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

20. The taxes and contributions for high-income individuals and companies should be increased

to provide for public education, healthcare and pensions.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

21. Water, energy and main natural resources should be under state control.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

22. The government should invest more resources to reduce social and economic inequalities.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

23. The government should invest more resources on national security.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- Don't know

24. How much do you trust the following institutions, for their beneficial role in society? Select one option for each institution.

a. Government

- Completely trust
- Somewhat trust
- Neutral [neither trust nor distrust]
- Somewhat distrust
- Completely distrust

b. Media

- Completely trust
- Somewhat trust
- Neutral [neither trust nor distrust]
- Somewhat distrust
- Completely distrust

c. Science

- Completely trust
- Somewhat trust
- Neutral [neither trust nor distrust]
- Somewhat distrust
- Completely distrust

25. Please, write down your name and your contact information (email address or telephone number), so that we can reach you about the citizen parliament recruitment.

Do note that if you do not provide this information, we will not be able to reach you and we cannot consider you a potential participant of the citizen parliament.

Name:

Email:

Telephone number :.....

Thank you for filling out the questionnaire! We will get back to you in due time to inform you about the recruitment of participants for the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy.

The information that you provide in this questionnaire will be collected only for the purposes of recruiting participants for the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy and will not be used for any other purpose nor will it be shared with third parties.

All data related to the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy is handled in compliance with GDPR. In case you wish to have your data removed or altered, or have concerns about stored data, please contact dr. Miloš Hroch at milos.hroch@fsv.cuni.cz.

Annex 1c: MIC - Questionnaire for screening recruits for Citizens' Parliament. MeDeMap Spring 2025

A short questionnaire is provided overleaf.

Please note:

- This will be administered by a researcher over the phone or in person
- The recruit will not have to write anything, the researcher will circle the answers the recruit provides
- The researcher will use this encounter to assess if the recruit is a vulnerable adult and the bone fides of the recruit and make notes on this page, if necessary.

NAME:

CONTACT DETAILS:

Researcher's name and date:

Researcher's notes:

Screening questionnaire for recruitment of participants in Citizens' Parliaments, Spring 2025

1. Age:

18-24 25-35 36-44 45-54 55-65 Over 65

2. Gender:

Man Woman Non-binary

3. Highest level of Education:

Primary school Secondary school

Third level If third level – what qualification?

4. How interested are you in political news?

Very interested Fairly interested

Not very interested Not interested at all

5. How much time do you spend on average reading or watching political news on a typical day?

Less than 10 minutes

10-30 minutes

30 minutes - 1 hour

More than 1 hour

6. Have you participated in any political elections (e.g. voted) in the last 5 years?

Yes

No

7. Are you a member of a political party, movement or political organisation?

Yes

No

8. Have you participated in demonstrations, protests, petitions or other political activities (including online) in the last 12 months?

Yes

No

9. Would you describe yourself as

Working Class

Middle Class

Other

10. Do you live in the city or in the country?

City

Country

Annex 2: Learning Objectives

The learning objectives of CP learning phases

By Nico Carpentier (CU), Laurence Monnot and Helmut Peissl (COMMIT)

20 January 2025

Preliminary remarks:

- This document is written as **support for the learning phases** of the MeDeMAP citizen parliaments (CPs), where CP1 plays a different (overview-generating) role, while CP2/3/4 have a more deepening role to play (by focussing on the three topics of (democracy and) media systems, media representation and media participation)
- The learning phase in the CPs will have **training videos and expert interventions**. One expert intervention will provide a broader overview of the issues at stake (with CP1 providing a broad overview of the democracy and media intersection, and CP2/3/4 focussing on the overview of their respective topics), and a second expert intervention offering a case study or example (which is necessarily narrower and more focussed). In the latter case, the expert can decide which type of media to address, but the CP organisers should avoid all case studies / examples being about one type of media (e.g., social media)
- **This document** is written in an **academic language** (as it feeds back into WP2 and deliverable 2.1); the language of the actual training videos and expert talks should be different – namely adjusted to the CP participants (as any good teacher would do).
- There is also a certain degree of overlap between the learning outcomes of different lectures (in particular between CP1 and CP2/3/4 respectively). This is intentional, as it will enhance the learning experience of the CP participants.
- This document will serve as a **guideline for the production of the training videos, and for producing the briefing of the two experts** who will speak during the CP meetings. For the briefing of the experts, this document should be adjusted to be more accessible, and examples of possible case studies (relevant in the national context of each CP) should be added to the briefing.

1. Expected learning outcomes for CP1: Media and Democracy

Participants are able to reflect on how the media nowadays fulfil their democratic roles and how their pro-democratic function can be fostered in order to develop proposals.

1/ CP1 – overview lecture (30 minutes)

General

- Participants are able to distinguish:

- what media are, and which different types of media currently exist (public media, market media and community media, which are using different infrastructures/platforms), ensuring that the CP participants have a common vocabulary to refer to particular types of media organisations
- Participants can appraise:
 - the five different roles of media can play in democracy (the informational, the control/watchdog role, the forum role, the representational role and the participatory role)
 - how minimalist-elitist democratic models emphasize mostly the informational, and the control/watchdog role, while the maximalist-participatory democratic models emphasize all five roles

The three topics – core concepts

- Participants have developed understanding of and can reflect on what:
 - a media system is
 - (media) representation is
 - (media) participation is

Key elements of the three topics

- CP participants understand how:
 - media are organised and regulated (and thus how they structured into media systems) impacts on their capacity to support democracy, what the limits of regulation are, and how there are different perspectives on media pluralism, media freedom and freedom of expression
 - media represent the social and the political (dis)allows them to support democracy, and how there are different perspectives on the pluriformity of these media representations
 - media facilitate participation in and through the media (dis)allows them to support democracy, and how there are different perspectives on their participatory intensities

2/ CP1 – case study relation media and democracy (20 minutes)

The case studies should illustrate the relation between democracy and media, preferably touching on the three perspectives of media systems, media representation and media participation. They should help participants to understand:

- how this example / case study activates one or more of the five different roles that media can play in democracy (the informational, the control/watchdog role, the forum role, the representational role and the participatory role)
- how this example / case study is particular, and takes a specific position in the political struggles over democracy and media (specifically in relation to the struggle between minimalist-elitist democratic models and the maximalist-participatory democratic models)

2. Expected learning outcomes for CP2: Media systems and regulation

Participants are able to reflect on how the media system is shaped by the regulation and the economic structures, and to develop proposals to support pro-democratic regulation.

1/ CP2 - overview lecture media systems (20 minutes) and training video 1 (10-15 minutes)

- CP participants understand:
 - what a media system is and how different types of media feature in it,
 - how a media system is connected to a capitalist economy
 - how a media system is regulated by governments
 - how the nature of a media system impacts on how a democracy can function, with a focus on:
 - differences in (financial) sustainability,
 - differences in (the protection of) structural (organisational) diversity and pluralism,
 - differences in (the protection of) media freedom and freedom of expression and
 - differences in (the protection against) symbolic violence (e.g., hate speech, harassment, libel, ...)
 - how the democratic nature of media systems (and its actors) can be threatened by attempts to colonize them (by internal and external actors, and by political and economic actors)

2/ CP2 - case study media systems (20 minutes)

Participants understand the role of media systems in democracy through a particular media-related example or case study. In particular, they understand:

- the context of the case study and its specificity (and limits)

- how this example / case study relates to issues of sustainability, structural (organisational) diversity and pluralism, media freedom and freedom of expression and/or symbolic violence
- how this example / case study relates to the political struggles over democracy and media (specifically related to the above-mentioned issues, and to the threats posed by the colonization of media)

3. Expected learning outcomes for CP3: Representation in the media

Participants are able to reflect on how representations frame information and how media could play an inclusive role instead of comforting exclusion, and to develop proposals to support diversity and complexity.

1/ CP3 – overview lecture media representations (20 minutes) and training video 2 (10-15 minutes)

- CP participants understand:
 - what the process of (media) representation is, how representations enter into information, how it is connected to power and ideology (and dominant actors), and how it is regulated by governments (keeping in mind that representation here refers to the concepts discursive meaning (“*Darstellung*” in German), and not its decision-making component (“*Vertretung*” in German))
 - how the nature of (media) representations impacts on a democracy, with a focus on:
 - the logic and consequences of stereotyping and symbolic annihilation, the mechanisms of (symbolic) inclusion and exclusion, the impact on the dignity of (and respect for) societal subgroups, and the importance of pluriform representations,
 - the importance of the representation of the political system and democracy itself
 - the broad media presence of representational issues, spanning many different genres (e.g., popular culture, crime reporting, ...)
 - the media’s ability to protect against reductionist representations, and to play an educational role in showing diversity and complexity
 - how reductionist representations can pose a threat towards democracy, by symbolically closing down the ‘corral’

2/ CP3 – case study media representations (20 minutes)

Participants understand the role of media representation in democracy through a particular media-related example or case study. In particular, they understand:

- the context of the case study and its specificity (and limits)
- how this example / case study relates to issues of inclusion/exclusion, dignity, pluriform/reductionist representations and/or the representation of the political
- how this example / case study relates to the political struggles over democracy and media (specifically related to the above-mentioned issues, and to the threats posed by reductionist representations and symbolic exclusions)

4. Expected learning outcomes for CP4: Participation in and through the media

Participants are able to reflect on how participation in and through the media functions, how it is restricted and how the media could play a role in protecting and developing pro-democratic participation.

1/ CP4 – overview lecture media participation (20 minutes) and training video 3 (10-15 minutes)

- CP participants understand:
 - what (media) participation is, what the difference between participation in and through the media is, how (media) participation is connected to power and ideology (and dominant actors), how there can be different participatory intensities in particular processes (ranging from minimalist to maximalist participation), and how more populist interpretations of media participation compete with approaches that allow for structural participation (e.g., through community media)
 - how the nature of (media) participation impacts on a democracy, with a focus on:
 - the importance of voice and the right to communicate
 - the limits that are imposed on voice, for instance, by how the diverse media infrastructures (and different types of media) function and the power centralizations embedded in them
 - the importance of a democratic media culture (made visible through its performance in mediated communication) and its participatory ethics, and the role of mediation and curation to protect them
 - how the strong reduction of participatory intensities (through silencing and lack of recognition, and the frustration and disenchantment it causes), and the undermining of (always situated) knowledges by disinformation and propaganda can pose threats for democracy

2/ CP4 – case study media participation (20 minutes)

Participants understand the role of media systems in democracy through a particular media-related example or case study. In particular, they understand:

- the context of the case study and its specificity (and limits)
- how this example / case study relates to issues of the right to communicate, the affordances of media infrastructures (and the different types of media), and/or a democratic media culture
- how this example / case study relates to the political struggles over democracy and media (specifically related to the above-mentioned issues, and to the threats posed by strong limitations on participatory intensities and the undermining of (situated) knowledges through disinformation/propaganda)

Annex 3: Indications for briefing the experts

This document briefly outlines the briefing instructions for the experts.

- **Information for experts**

The experts will be informed about the MeDeMAP project, the aims of the CP, the participants and the expected learning outcomes.

Participants: 20 citizens from different socio-demographic and educational backgrounds with no previous knowledge of media and democracy. The participants will be asked to reflect on their needs to use the media in a way that supports more democracy and propose resolutions.

Purposes: The aim is to provide participants with relevant knowledge to help them identify issues at stake on which they can develop resolutions.

Videos: The three learning videos will be used not only as learning material for the participants but also as thematic orientation for the experts and should be shared with them.

- **Experts' inputs as part of the learning phase**

The experts' inputs conform part of the learning phase together with the learning videos and other information documents. Like in the videos, the topics covered by the experts are the three core themes addressed in the CPs: media system and regulation, media representation and participation in and through the media. The experts' contributions, videos and documentation aim to help participants make decisions based on informed deliberation.

- **Profile of the experts**

We propose having two complementary presentations in each session, with Expert 1 to provide a broad overview of the issues at stake (nonetheless with concrete examples and not just theory)

Expert 2 to present cases that illustrate the day topic (narrowing the lens). The cases should deal with different types of media.

Team members can also take on the role of experts if this makes sense in terms of content. In general, a gender balance of experts is recommended.

- **Tasks of the experts**

20 min. input: The experts should give an input of about 20 minutes (up to 30 minutes for Expert 1 on Day1), addressing the issues described in the learning objectives below in a didactic and lively way for an audience of uninformed citizens.

The presentations should be easily understandable for all participants, didactic and illustrated with concrete examples.

Availability for Q&A: Experts will be asked to be available after their presentation either for a Q&A session or for answering questions from the small groups working on the subtopic lists for about 1.5 hours.

Short note with key points: Experts will be asked to provide a short abstract of their presentation or slides with comments (max. 2 pages).

Technical setting and material: The experts should be informed about the setting of the room. They should be asked to communicate their presentation in advance and indicate what technical equipment they need (beamer, flip-chart, etc.).

Annex 4: Model CP-script COMMIT

CP Script COMMIT 06.02.2025

When	How long	Purpose	What	Details
CP 1		Presentation of the CP on Media and Democracy.	Agreement on purpose and process. Introduction to main theme.	
		Preparation of the room	Setting the room. Technical check. Control of material. Check-in team.	chair circle/group tables. name tags...
9.30 AM		Arrival of participants and get together		
10:00 AM	5 min	Start and welcome	Welcome & orientation	Welcome by MeDeMap team. Call to participate
10:05 AM	10 min		Presentation of facilitation. Presentation of observers	
10:15 AM	30 min	Check-in Emotional and cognitive arrival in the room. All voices heard.	Speed dialogs on 3 questions with 3 different people OR line-up according to criteria and discussion of impulse questions: e.g. socio-demographic/ preferences/ content-related OR short exchange at the tables (if tables).	Possible questions: Why did you decide to take part? how long did you think about taking part? ...which media you consume regularly/ how you inform yourself ...where do you live (country - city), ...pets, ...etc.
10:45 AM	10 min	Agenda & how do we want to work together	Facilitation presents agenda. Facilitation presents frame for discussions.	Framing/attitude: openness and curiosity; accepting and exploring differences and different perspectives => getting smarter together, helping each other to think, and naming differences.
10:55 AM	10 min	Orientation: What is MeDeMap? Theme and 3 topics. What is a CP? -->Participants know the purpose of the CP and the structure; participants understand that their contributions are valued; participants understand their role.	Input from MeDeMAP team: - Overview of research project & purpose, - why is this topic important? - why do we need the CP? - what is our invitation to the participants?	Beamer: PP with core information, CP sequence, key question(s). max. 4-5 slides CHECK: who makes the input?
11:05 AM	10 min	Q&A	Small groups (SG) discussing questions (5') asking questions (5')	Documentation

CP1 11.20 AM	40 min	Rules for co-creative discussions -->safe space for open and respectful communication	Introduction (5') Group work: establish conversation rules (20') - 2 groups - each group collects their "Yes" and "No" (max 4-5) - write on moderation cards - collect cards on pinboard and compare (15') - Have them agree in turn in the circle	Hand out moderation cards. If table groups: 2 tables
12:00	20 min	<i>BREAK</i>		
12:20	25 min	Learning phase 1 -->Participants have basic knowledge about "Media and Democracy"	Main input / overview on Media & Democracy	Beamer. Expert has been briefed.
12:45	15 min		Small groups discussing questions (5') asking questions (10')	
13:00	60 min	<i>LUNCH</i>	<i>Preparation of the tables & materials for World cafe</i>	<i>4 pinboards for main themes and sub-topics</i>
14:00	60 min	Learning phase 2: introduction to sub-topics -->Participants have an overview of the 3 topics. They have information about the relevance of the topics for their own lives and democracy.	3 inputs of 10', each followed by 10' Q&A	Check who makes the inputs. Beamer? Handouts? Notepads for participants
15:00	85 min	Mindmap of questions --> Participants process all inputs and develop first ideas for questions they want to work on in during CP for all 3 subtopics. (Result: first mapping of work topics)	Introduction to World Café (10'). 4 topic tables. 3 rounds. Table host stays at table. Other participants rotate. Round 1: "What do you think about <i>media & democracy (and subtopics 1, 2, 3) now?</i> ". What issues do you care about? (25') Round 2: "What questions or issues would you like to work on?" (25') Round 3: repeat question 2 and harvest (25')	4 tables with large table sheet. A4 sheets for collecting results. Pens. Prepare harvest sheets with instructions on how to formulate topics 1) Topic: What do you want to work on/what issues do you want to address? 2) Why is this topic important to you? Option 1: Limited number of sheets. 3 sheets/table = 12 sheets Option 2: as many sheets as needed, then prioritize
16:25	20 min	<i>BREAK</i>	<i>Table hosts prepare presentation of results with sheet of papers to stick on pin walls.</i>	<i>4 pin walls with titles</i>

CP1 16:45	45 min	Presentation of results (lists of subtopics). Priority setting -->Participants have established a list of topics for which they want to develop recommendations	Introduction Step 1: - 4 table hosts present the results of their table (4x3' = 12') - Harvest sheets are collected and pinned to topic pinboards. Clustering by MeDeMap team (approx. 8') Step 2: Prioritization of subtopics (25') - participants are given sticky dots: "In your opinion, what are the 5/7/9 (?) most important topics for which the CP should develop resolutions?" - Participants stick their dots on pinwall - count, write down the total	Sticky dots distributed to participants CHECK: how many dots?
17:30	30 min	Wrap-up and check-out --> cognitive and emotional closing. Information on next steps. Outlook for the next meetings	Next steps and organizational information (MeDeMAP Team) Check-out: one sentence per person "What do you take away from the first CP?"	
18:00		End of CP1		

When	How long	Purpose	What	Details
		CP2 & CP3		
10		Preparation of the room and team check-in	Setting the room. Technical check. Control of material.	Table groups (4 tables with 5 people each)
9.30 AM		Arrival of participants and get together		
10:00 AM	10 min	Start and welcome	Welcome from MeDeMAP and from facilitation	
10:10 AM	15 min	Check-in Emotional and cognitive arrival in the room. All voices heard.	<i>Speed dialogs?</i>	
10:25 AM	50 min	Learning phase: Input on media systems and regulation (or on topic 2) -->Participants have enough knowledge to develop resolutions	Presentation of videos and experts by MeDeMAP team (5') Video on topic. (10') Expert input (overview). (20') Expert input cases. (15')	Beamer. Experts have been briefed.
		Q&A		

11:15 AM	15-20 min		Small groups discussing questions (5-10') asking questions (10-15')	
11.35 AM	15 min	<i>BREAK</i>	<i>Preparation of the pin walls/ flip charts with subtopic list from CP1</i>	<i>2 more chairs for experts.</i>
CP2 & CP3 11:50	40 min	Enhance and refine subtopic list 1 (or 2) => final list of working questions for subtopic	Intro: Recall results of CP1 (10') Work in 3-4 small groups (30') - “What questions do you want to work on after listening to the inputs?” - Each group identifies 4-5 topics and writes them on moderation cards	Experts remain in the room and are available to answer questions, but do not actively participate in discussions at the tables. Moderation cards, pens Table moderation for 3 groups, otherwise instructions for participants
12:30	30 min	Presentation of the new questions for subtopic 1 and clustering	Introduction - Each SG presents its topic suggestions (5'/group) - all cards are collected and put up on a pin board (clustering by MeDeMAP Team)	Approx. 20 new topics (controlled by allocation of moderation cards)
13:00	20 min	Prioritization and allocation of working groups --> list of topics is fixed	Introduction - Participants receive sticky dots and stick them on - count, write down sums - put the list of topics in the appropriate order	Distribute sticky dots Check: decide in advance if participants choose a cluster of their choice for afternoon or are assigned during the lunch break
13:20	60 min	<i>LUNCH</i>	<i>If needed, finish clustering and find cluster names (MeDeMAP team)</i> <i>Either</i> <i>a) Participants stick their names to a cluster => (new group distribution, same size)</i> <i>b) Allocation of participants according to heterogeneity of groups)</i>	<i>Important: equal distribution number of topics/table!</i>

14:20	90 min	Drafting resolutions	<p>Introduction: explanation of procedure incl. how to deal with disagreement (10')</p> <p>Work in 3 Small groups (SG) of 6-7 people (40')</p> <p>Objective: develop 3-4 recommendations, write on cards (important: complete sentences)</p> <p>Determine SG speaker</p> <p>Group moderation.- Ritual dissent/ feedback through neighboring table (15'): SG speaker goes to a neighboring table, presents recommendations and listens to feedback on them- Integration of the feedback (30'): SG speaker tells own home group the results, SG incorporates them to improve recommendations: What is new? What are we going to ignore? What do we take into account?</p>	<p>Template for recommendations and template for dissenting opinion</p> <p>to decide: a) 3 "large" groups with table moderation or 4 parallel groups => self moderation, instructions. (Moderators as trouble-shooters)</p> <p>CHECK: what happens if there is no consensus?</p> <p>Suggestion => what needs to change for you to participate? (consensus)=> If no solution is found, the resolution is dropped. Ritual dissent: if logistically/timely possible, feedback from mixed tables</p>
16:00	20 min	<i>BREAK</i>	<i>All suggestions are put up on pinboards</i> <i>SG speakers prepare for presentation</i>	
CP2 & CP3 16:20	30 min	Presentation of resolutions	<p>Introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SG speakers present the results of their groups (with 3-4 recommendations each = max. 16 recommendations) - Comprehension questions <p>Decision about proposed recommendations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - confirm - veto/ majority vote? if no consensus then majority vote plus dissenting opinions. (qualified majority vote?) 	Pin walls and pins
16:50	40 min	Vote on resolutions	<p>Introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the voting method - Participants receive sticky notes in two or three colours - Sticky notes for reasons for vetoes - Summary of results (what was accepted, what was rejected) 	<p>MeDeMap: what are the requirements for voting? (simple majority/ qualified majority)</p> <p>green = approval/ affirmation</p> <p>red = veto</p> <p>Check: are all proposals accepted that do not have a veto (or vice versa) or should there also be abstentions?</p> <p>Add sticky notes for reasons for vetoes</p>

17:30	30 min	Wrap-up and check-out 10	Next steps and organizational information (MeDeMAP Team) Check-out: one sentence per person “What do you take away?”		
18:00		End of CP2 / CP3			

When	How long	Purpose	What	Details	
CP4		Subtopic 3 and closure			
10		<i>Preparation of the room and team check-in</i>	<i>Setting the room. Technical check. Control of materials.</i>	<i>Table groups (4 tables with 5 people each)</i>	
9.30 AM		Arrival of participants and get together			
10:00 AM	10 min	Start and welcome	Welcome from MeDeMAP and from facilitation		
10:10 AM	15 min	Check-in Emotional and cognitive arrival in the room. All voices heard.	<i>Speed dialogs?</i>		
10:25 AM	50 min	Learning phase: topic 3 -->Participants have enough knowledge to develop resolutions	Presentation of videos and experts by MeDeMAP team (5') Video on topic. (10') Expert input (overview). (20') Expert input cases. (15')	Beamer. Experts have been briefed.	
11:15 AM	15-20 min	Q&A	Small groups discussing questions (5-10') asking questions (10-15')		
11.30 AM	15 min	BREAK	<i>Preparation of the pin walls/ flip charts with subtopic list from CP1</i>	<i>2 more chairs for experts.</i>	
11:45	40 min	Enhance and refine subtopic list => final list of working questions for subtopic	Intro: Recall results of CP1 (10') Work in 3-4 small groups (30') - “What questions do you want to work on after listening to the inputs?” - Each group identifies 4-5 topics and writes them on moderation cards	Experts remain in the room and are available to answer questions, but do not actively participate in discussions at the tables. Moderation cards, pens Table moderation for 3 groups, otherwise instructions for participants	
12:25	30 min	Presentation of the new questions for subtopic 3 and clustering	Introduction - Each small group presents its topic suggestions (5'/group) - all cards are collected and put up on a pin board (clustering by MeDeMAP Team)	Approx. 20 new topics (controlled by allocation of moderation cards)	

12:55	20 min	Prioritization and allocation of working groups --> list of topics is fixed	Intro - Participants receive sticky dots and stick them on - count, write down sums - put the list of topics in the appropriate order	Distribute sticky dots Check: decide in advance if participants choose a cluster of their choice for afternoon or are assigned during the lunch break
13:15	60 min	LUNCH	<i>If needed, finish clustering and find cluster names (MeDeMAP team)</i> <i>Either</i> <i>a) Participants stick their names to a cluster => (new group distribution, same size)</i> <i>b) Allocation of participants according to heterogeneity of groups)</i>	<i>Important: equal distribution number of topics/table</i>
CP4 14:15	95 min	Drafting resolutions	Introduction: explanation of procedure incl. how to deal with disagreement (10') Work in 3 small groups of 6-7 people (40') Objective: develop 3-4 recommendations, write on cards (important: complete sentences) Determine SG speaker Group moderation.- Ritual dissent/ feedback through neighboring table (15'): Group speaker goes to a neighboring table, presents recommendations and listens to feedback on them- Integration of the feedback (30'): speaker tells own home group the results, SG incorporates them to improve recommendations: What is new? What are we going to ignore? What do we take into account?	Template for recommendations and template for dissenting opinionsto decide: a) 3 large groups with table moderation or 4 parallel groups => self moderation, instructions. (Moderators as trouble-shooters) CHECK: what happens if there is no consensus? Suggestion => what needs to change for you to participate? (consensus)=> If no solution is found, the resolution is dropped. Ritual dissent: if logistically/timely possible, feedback from mixed tables
15:50	15 min	BREAK	All suggestions are put up on pinboards Speakers prepare for presentation	
16:05	30 min	Presentation of resolutions	Introduction - Speakers present the results of their groups (with 3-4 recommendations each = max. 16 recommendations) - Comprehension questions Decision about proposed recommendations - confirm - veto/ majority vote? if no consensus then majority vote plus dissenting opinions. (qualified majority vote?)	Pin walls and pins

16:35	40 min	Vote on resolutions	<p>Introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the voting method - Participants receive sticky notes in two or three colours - Sticky notes for reasons for vetoes - Summary of results (what was accepted, what was rejected) 	<p>MeDeMap: what are the requirements for voting? (simple majority/ qualified majority)</p> <p>green = approval/ affirmation red = veto</p> <p>Check: are all proposals accepted that do not have a veto (or vice versa) or should there also be abstentions?</p> <p>Add sticky notes for reasons for vetoes</p>
17:15	5 min	<i>SHORT BREAK</i>	<p><i>Circle for completion of the CP. Tidying up the room.</i></p> <p><i>Hang up the list of resolutions.</i></p>	
17:20	35	Wrap-up of CP and selection of 2 representatives	<p>MeDeMAP team informs about dates and next steps (incl. sending of results)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Election of the representatives . Take a group photo 	<p>Check: Procedure for selecting the 2 representatives? (draw lots? elect? ask electronically in advance who is interested?)</p> <p>Sociocratic election?</p> <p>Group photo</p>
17:55	25 min	Check-out--> cognitive and emotional closing.	<p>Thanks.Check-out: one sentence per person "What do you take away?"</p>	
18:20	20 min	End of CP. Celebration.		<p>Toast, finger food</p>

Annex 5: Model CP-Script CU

MeDeMAP CP script

Nico Carpentier

Draft version 3 – 21 January 2025

Activity	Start moment	End moment	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
Before CP1					
Make the three three training videos available	15 February	They stay online for the entire duration of the project	The three training videos explain the three thematic areas (media systems, media representations & media participation)		Platform
Make informational texts available	15 February	They stay online for the entire duration of the project	A limited of number texts, explaining the three thematic areas		Platform
Consent forms	15 February	Start of CP1	The final versions of the consent forms, ready to be signed at the start of CP1		Platform

CP & Timeslot	Activity	Duration	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
CP1					
Morning 9:30	Introduction	20m	<u>Circle</u> Each person present briefly introduces themselves, with two questions: name and reason(s) for being there.		
Morning	Briefing	20m	<u>Circle</u> The main moderator (MM) gives an overview of the CP process (also ensuring informed consent forms are signed)		
Morning	Agreement on CP modus operandi	20m	<u>Circle</u> 1/ Agreement on objectives & procedures: The MM		

			<p>describes the structure of the CP (and the agenda) and checks agreement</p> <p>2/ Establishment of discussion and decision rules: The MM outlines the core principles of CP interaction (listen, speak when you have the floor, no judgement, connect to others) and the balance between consensus-seeking and the use of qualified majority for resolutions (e.g., 2/3). The MM asks to confirm the 2/3 vote rule, and a rule on what to do with a tied vote (<i>to be specified</i>).</p>		
Morning	Break	15m			

Morning 11:00	Learning stage (general – 3 themes)	5m	<u>Lecture</u> MM introduces the experts and (briefly) explains the procedure and learning outcomes		
		25m	Screening of the 3 training videos		Projection with sound
		30m	Expert 1 (overview of D&M)		Possible projection
		20m	Expert 2 (case study as illustration)		Possible projection
Lunch 12:00					
Afternoon 13:00	Learning stage (general)	60m	<u>Working groups</u> 1/MM splits participants into 4 working groups to prepare questions for experts 2/ Q&A with experts (and then the experts leave)		
Afternoon		30m	<u>Circle</u>		

14:00	Establishing subtopics for the three themes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MM starts with guiding question: “How can media improve to better serve democracy?” - each participant fills out 1 card each, explains it in a <i>tour de table</i> and places the card in centre 		
		15m	break		
		60m	<u>World café (rotation model)</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MM divides the participants into 3 small groups - on basis of three guiding questions: “How can the media system / media representation / media participation be improved to better serve democracy?” - one table for each of the three questions - participants rotate, except for question owners (also CP participants) - one card for each answer 		
		15m	break		
		30m	<u>Clustering into subtopics</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -the tables (and the answers) remain -MM explains what subtopics are -each CP participants selects one table, and the answers are clustered collectively into subtopics 		
Afternoon 16:30	Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings	30m	<u>Closing circle</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -<i>Tour de table</i> with short statements about what the CP participants take home 		

			- Briefing on next steps (online and next meeting)		
End 17:00					

Activity	Start moment	End moment	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
After CP1 and before CP2					
Minutes of CP1	After CP1	Published 1 week after CP1	Short (factual) minutes of the meeting, focussing on the three subtopic lists	Minutes uploaded on platform	Platform
Short feedback survey	After CP1	Before CP2	A very short survey for the CP participants, about the experiences of CP1	Survey answers	Survey question part of platform
Subtopics cleaning proposal	After minutes are published	Before CP2	MeDeMAP team analyses the subtopics and respectfully enhance quality, uploads it, and informs CP participants to read it	Improved three lists (as proposal) (+ four A1 prints)	Platform

CP & Timeslot	Activity	Duration	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
CP2 (media systems)					
Morning 9:00	Check-in	15m	<u>Circle</u> -Briefing on day's agenda		
Morning	Learning stage (media systems theme)	5m	<u>Lecture</u> MM introduces the experts and (briefly) explains the procedure and learning outcomes		
		10m	Screening of one training video (on media systems)		Projection with sound
		30m	Expert 1 (overview of democracy and media systems)		Possible projection
		20m	Expert 2 (case study as illustration)		Possible projection

Morning	Break	15m			
Morning 10:30	Confirmation subtopics T1 list	60m	<p><u>Small group discussion</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MM shows list of T1 subtopics from day 1 (the version that was improved by MeDeMAP team) and explains changes - The list is kept visible (via projection and printed on four flipcharts) - MM divides the participants in four groups, where each group: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * confirms each item on the list (or crosses them out) one by one * discusses the inclusion of new subtopics; if the group agrees, new subtopics are added to the respective flowcharts 		Projection and four flipcharts
		15m	Break	List of new (proposed) subtopics	
Morning 11:30	Finalization of subtopic list	30m	<p><u>Plenary voting</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MM explains decision making mechanism (if one group deletes = keep; if two groups propose deletion = vote; if three/four groups proposes deletion = deletion) - MM goes over original list, subtopic per subtopic, and decides which ones to keep, following the outlined decision-making procedure and the discussion at the previous session - MM shows the aggregated list of new subtopics (produced by the MeDeMAP team during the break, on basis of previous session), and the CP participants 		Projection

			decide on which ones to add (same decision-making procedure)		
Morning 12:00	Prioritization of subtopics	20m	<p><u>Dot-voting</u> (or dotmocracy)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The final subtopic list is projected on a wall (or one flipchart is used) -Each participant is given five dots, which they can stick to whatever subtopic they want (from 5 dots for one, to 1 dots for five subtopics) -Mods count the votes for each subtopic 		Projection on wall where people can stick dots
Lunch 12:30		60m		MeDeMAP Team creates ordered list on basis of votes	
Afternoon 13:00	Discussion subtopics and creation resolutions	60m	<p><u>World café (rotation model)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -MM divides the participants in 4 small groups -The first four subtopics are allocated to one table each -Each small group rotates into these four subtopics -At a table, the first small group writes one (or two) resolutions (on a resolution form), on the table's subtopic, clearly formulating "what needs to change (or be strengthened) for media to better serve democracy" -At the next iteration, the small group can adjust the formulation of existing resolutions, or add (only) one new resolution (as long as it's (very) different) 		Resolution form (paper)

			-there are five iterations, so each small group ends up at the table where it started		
		15m	break	MedeMAP team collects resolutions	
		60m	<u>Circle</u> All resolutions are projected (or on a flipchart) and friendly amendments on particular resolutions can be proposed by an individual CP participant. A friendly amendment requires a (fairly) precise formulation from the person who proposes it. If no consensus about the amendment, there is a simple majority vote on which version (the original or the amended version) to select		Projection
Afternoon 16:00	Voting resolutions	30m	<u>Plenary voting</u> - All proposed resolutions are projected on screen (or on a flipchart) - The MM organises a vote for each resolution, if there is no clear consensus (using the 2/3 majority, or other majority system agreed before)		
Afternoon 16:30	Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings	30m	<u>Closing circle</u> - <i>Tour de table</i> with short statements about what the CP participants take home - Briefing on next steps (online and next meeting)		
End 17:00					

Activity	Start moment	End moment	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
After CP2 and before CP3					
Minutes of CP2	After CP2	Published 1 week after CP2	Short (factual) minutes of the meeting, focussing on the resolutions and voting results	Minutes uploaded on platform	Platform
Resolution upload	After CP2	Uploaded 1 week after CP2	Each individual resolution is uploaded on the confirmatory/dissenting opinions section of the platform	Resolutions separately uploaded on platform	Resolution response part of platform
Invitation for confirmatory/dissenting opinions to CP participants	One week after CP2	Before CP3	Participants are invited to go to the online platform to express confirmation or dissent with resolutions. If they have access problems, the MeDeMAP team will assist	Communication to CP participants	Resolution response part of platform
Short feedback survey	After CP2	Before CP3	A very short survey for the CP participants, about the experiences of CP2	Survey answers	Survey question part of platform

CP & Timeslot	Activity	Duration	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
CP3 (media representations)					
Same structure as CP2					

Activity	Start moment	End moment	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
After CP3 and before CP4					
Same structure as in-between CP2 and CP3					

CP & Timeslot	Activity	Duration	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
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CP4 (media participation)					
Same structure as CP2 except for the last session (“Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings”), which is replaced by:					
Afternoon 16:30	Wrap-up, thank you & and next (dissemination) steps	30m	<u>Closing circle</u> - <i>Tour de table</i> with short statements about what the CP participants take home - Briefing on next steps: the national resolution presentation, the European presentation, ...		
End 17:00					

Activity	Start moment	End moment	Description	Material outcomes	Tech Needs
After CP4					
Same structure as in-between CP2 and CP3					

Annex 6: Facilitation tools or techniques and references

- **Materials**

The following materials are recommended for facilitation of the CPs:

- 2-4 flip charts plus paper
- 4-6 bulletin boards (pinboards or surface for the posting of group results) covered with large paper,
- Pins
- Moderation Cards
- Sticky Notes (post-it notes to stick on flip chart)
- Markers and felt-tip pens
- Scotch Tape
- Name Badges

- **Some facilitation tools or techniques that could be used during the CPs**

Dialogue rules

Chris Corrigan, an influential practitioner of the Art of Hosting has summarized the main principles for practicing dialogue (2004, p. 25). These are examples of rules CP participants might agree with:

- Each member should have his/her say. ("Your opinion is important.")
- Suspend judgments and assumptions
- Accept that divergent opinions are okay
- Link and connect ideas

Speaking and listening rules

- Speak one at a time
- Speak with intention.
- Listen to each other with attention. (We do not interrupt each other.)
- Listen together for insights and deeper questions

Have fun!

The circle and checking in and out (at the beginning and end of each session)

The circle format puts all members on an equal footing and encourages sharing. Leadership rotates among all circle members, responsibility is shared, the group is called to rely on wholeness rather than personal agendas.

The circle is especially recommended for phases such as check-in and check-out, and for plenary discussions to reach consensus. (Corrigan, 2004, p. 30)

- "Checking in" at the beginning of each session allows for a smooth introduction and presentation of each member.

- "Closing the circle" by "checking out" before ending the session provides a formal end to the meeting while giving each member an opportunity to reflect on the process and outcomes.

How does it work? The circle host typically opens the circle with a gesture to indicate that the circle is about to begin.

In the center of the circle are usually objects that represent the intention of the circle and can be used as "talking pieces".

A volunteer takes the initiative and passes the intention to his or her neighbor. If a person is not ready to speak, the turn is passed, and another opportunity is offered after others have spoken.

The talking piece is passed from hand to hand. The person holding the piece is invited to speak and everyone else to listen.

The Guardian: Having a circle member volunteer to be the guardian can be helpful in bringing the circle back to the intention.

Setting: A room free of tables that can hold the group in a circle. Talking pieces can be placed in the center.

Other tools: a gentle noise maker to remind people of the time or the end of the session.

Speed dialogue

Participants at a speed dialogue have a series of short one-to-one discussions with different partners (it gives the opportunity to have discussions with more people).

The Pro-Action Café (topic café)

- to establish first draft of 3 subtopic lists on Day 1 (afternoon)
- to develop proposals on Day 2, Day 3, and Day 4 (afternoon)

The Pro-Action Café technique encourages co-creation. As in the World Café, one participant hosts a table. The host briefly shares key insights, questions, and ideas with new table members, and then allows people to develop questions and suggestions. After participants have moved through the rounds, the harvest can be shared in plenary.

In the Pro-Action Café, participants visit different tables in several rounds. Each table is dedicated to one topic. To create a dynamic flow of ideas, each round can focus on specific questions.

- **References and resources for facilitating / The Art of Hosting**

Corrigan, C. (2020, January 4). The Four-Fold Practice, meeting design, and facilitation/3. <https://www.chriscorrigan.com/parkinglot/the-four-fold-practice-meeting-design-and-facilitation/>

Corrigan, C. Art of Hosting. (2012). The Art of Hosting. (informal guide for the Vancouver Island Aboriginal Transition Team based on material developed by the Art of Hosting practitioner's community). <https://b-m-institute.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Corrigan-Art-of-Hosting-Fieldguide.pdf>

Brown, J, Isaacs, D, et al. (2005). The World Cafe, Shaping Our Futures Through Conversations That Matter.

Minnesota Communities Caring for Children. (2018). The Art of Hosting Conversations that Matter. Participatory Leadership Tools for Community Change. Workbook. <https://familywiseservices.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Art-of-Hosting-Workbook.pdf>

Websites

Art of Hosting. www.artofhosting.org

Art of Hosting Ning. <http://artofhosting.ning.com/>

Chris Corrigan. <https://www.chriscorrigan.com/parkinglot/facilitation-resources/>

Videos

Art of Hosting. <https://artofhosting.org/resources-2/videos/>

The Circle Way. <https://www.thecircleway.net/resource-videos>

Art of Hosting Ning. <http://artofhosting.ning.com/video/video/listFeatured>

Podcasts

NewDemocracy is an Australian research organization focusing on citizens' participation collaborating with local, national and international institutions for the organization of CPs. The podcast serie produced by Lyn Carson is particularly inspirational

NewDemocracy. <https://www.newdemocracy.com.au/category/library/podcast/>

NewDemocracy. Episode 40: Reflecting on deliberation and valuable techniques with Kath Fisher - newDemocracy Foundation. <https://www.newdemocracy.com.au/2021/01/04/episode-40-reflecting-on-deliberation-and-valuable-techniques-with-kath-fisher/>

NewDemocracy. Episode 23: Long-form deliberation - Perspectives from experienced and new facilitators with Kaela Scott and Dominic Ward - newDemocracy Foundation. <https://www.newdemocracy.com.au/2020/08/05/episode-23-long-form-deliberation-perspectives-from-experienced-and-new-facilitators-with-kaela-scott-and-dominic-ward/>

Annex 7: CP Platform - Structure

Annex 8: CP Platform – Structure specs

TITLE: The Citizens' Parliament Platform (MeDeMAP)
Structure, Specs Version 2.2
(17 February 2025, by JS and NC)

BASIC INFORMATION

- Citizens' Parliament = CP
- 4 CPs (CP1 to CP4) in each of the five countries: Austria, Czech Republic, Germany; Ireland, Slovenia
- Only Germany: Online CPs

Timetable:

Country	Place	CP1	CP2	CP3	CP4	Public Event
Austria	Vienna	22.3.	5.4.	26.4	17.5	
Czech Rep.	different cities	15.3.	5.4.	26.4.	17.5	
Germany	online					
Ireland	Limerick	22.3.	5.4.	26.4.	10.5	
Slovenia	Ljubljana	15.3.	29.3.	12.4.	10.5.	

Partners websites on CP-activities and useful information:

- Austria <https://medemap.commit.at/>
- Czech Republic <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/>
- Germany
- Ireland
- Slovenia

Contacts: Josef.Seethaler@oeaw.ac.at; Helmut Peissl hp@commit.at; Nico Carpentier nico.carpentier@fsv.cuni.cz; Rosemary Day rosemary.day@mic.ul.ie; Brankica Petković Brankica.Petkovic@mirovni-institut.si

Additional country organizers:

Czech Republic: Vaia Doudaki - vaia.doudaki@fsv.cuni.cz; Miloš Hroch - milos.hroch@fsv.cuni.cz; Štěpán Šanda - stepan.sanda@fsv.cuni.cz

LOCATION

OEAW Server

ACCESS

	<i>Organizers</i> <i>(Note: Country Organizers are the organizers of a national CPs)</i>	<i>Participants</i>
Availability	28 February 2025 Entire duration of the project (28 February 2026)	15 March 2025 July 2025 (= 1 month after end of CP4)
Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Password-protected (individual PWs) • Email address (= username) must be provided; URL and PW are provided via email • Option to apply for a new PW (provision of new PW may take up to a day) 	
User rights	Not restricted	Partly restricted to the <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • read (*), • download (**) and • fill-in (***) function
Landing page	Central landing page, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • which gives access to the five national CP landing sub-pages, which gives access to the three main sections 	Redirected directly to 'their' national CP page (= one of the five landing sub-pages) in the national language (Czech, English, German, Slovenian), which gives access to the three main sections Redirect decided on the basis of login (name or email)

LANDING PAGE

gives access to the five national CP landing sub-pages

NATIONAL CP PAGES

give access to the three main sections

Bold and underlined: Titles

Section 1: The document archive

<i>Content</i>	<i>Specs</i>
Static content	<p>From 1 March 2025:</p> <p>Videos – Training videos explaining the three thematic areas * The same three videos are to be embedded on the 4 national subpages, and the participants select the right language. A brief explanation (in the local language) is needed!</p> <p>Democracy and Media Systems https://vimeo.com/826667801 pw: commitvid Media and Participation https://vimeo.com/890787535 - pw: commitvid Media and Representation https://vimeo.com/1053501291 - pw: commitvid</p> <p>Reading – PDFs of texts explaining the three thematic areas – PRINTING must be possible * ** <i>Czech texts already available in folder “Reading”</i></p> <p>Consent form – PDF * ** - The BLANK consent form will be available on the CP platform beforehand, for participants to download them. - The participants should be warned beforehand. - The national partners are responsible for collecting the SIGNED forms. <i>Czech form already available in folder “Forms and practical information”</i></p> <p>Optional: Practical information – PDF) * ** <i>Czech info already available in folder “Forms & Information”!</i></p> <p>Links to national WP6 websites <i>Already available: Austria https://medemap.commit.at/; Czech Republic https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/</i></p> <p>After CP1:</p> <p>Subtopics – Three PDFs of lists of subtopics * ** Minutes of the 1st Citizens’ Parliament * **</p>

	<p>After CP2: <u>Minutes of the 2nd Citizens' Parliament</u> * ** <u>Photos</u> – of CP2 * **</p> <p>After CP3: <u>Minutes of the 3rd Citizens' Parliament</u> * ** <u>Photos</u> – of CP3 * **</p> <p>After CP4: <u>Minutes of the 4th Citizens' Parliament</u> * ** <u>Photos</u> – of CP4 * **</p>
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Section 2: Feedback survey

Content	Specs
Interactive content	<p>After CP1-4:</p> <p>Surveys – Survey questions answering form (about experiences with CP)*** → “THANK YOU FOR ANSWERING” page</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is an online survey for the members of the CP that will start after the first CP took place and that then will be repeated 3 times (after each CP), with one slight modification after the CP1 survey. In other words, each member of the CP will be asked to fill out 4 different surveys, with (almost) the same six questions. Each survey will generate a separate data file. • Questions need to be translated into the 3 other languages, as the survey will be offered in each of the national sections of the CP platform. So, in total, there will be 20 short surveys for the 4 national CPs (Czech, Slovene, Irish and Austrian) and the online CP (Germany). • Each question (there are six questions in total) needs to have a field (to answer) for textual input, without a word limit. Text fields can be left open if a participant wants to (there should be no requirement to answer). • Once the answers to a survey are submitted, they cannot be changed. • Results of the survey should NOT be visible on the CP platform itself; only the organizers should have access. <p><i>Czech and English questions already available in folder “Survey questions”!</i></p>

Section 3: Resolution feedback

Content	Specs
<p>Static content</p> <p>Interactive content</p>	<p>After CP2-4:</p> <p><u>Resolutions of the 2nd Citizens' Parliament</u> * **</p> <p><u>Resolutions of the 3rd Citizens' Parliament</u> * **</p> <p><u>Resolutions of the 4th Citizens' Parliament</u> * **</p> <p>Form (= not visible for Participants) where Organizers can upload each separate resolution (after each CP)</p> <p>Form for Participants, where each resolution is visible (non-changeable), with a text field (max. 500 words) for each resolution, where they can express their confirmatory/dissenting opinions. ***</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One form for all resolutions. • Once posted, the answers of the one participant remain visible to that participant only. • If possible, a notification is sent to the country organizers when an opinion is uploaded. • If possible, participants can later change their answers until the website closes.

Annex 9: Guidelines for blog posts

Deliverable: At least 6 blog posts. Before the start of the CPs, after each CP session, and after the national presentation.

Addressed to medemap@commit.at

Finality: Informing. Posts in English on the MeDeMAP blog hosted by COMMIT and shared on LinkedIn and Bluesky. Contributions published on partner websites in local languages. COMMIT will also publish an overview of partner CPs on EPALE.

Date and time:

- First blog post: around 2 weeks before the start of the CP.
- Blog posts after CP1, CP2, CP3, CP4: before Friday 10.00 am of the week after CP
- Blog post after national presentation: at least 1 week after national presentation

Format:

- Maximum 3500 signs (min. 1500 signs).
- At least two photos (with photo credits).

Structure:

- Title (short, summarizes what took place)
- Lead (a summary paragraph of key information)
- Paragraphs with subtitles

Content:

These blog posts will report on the CPs outcomes and on the process (learning, deliberation, adoption). Blog post 1 will present the purpose and the organization of the CP.

Answer the "5 Ws": What, Who, When, Where, Why (and How) of a story, taking into account the "news value" for the target audience.

- **What:** the CP event.
 - Blog post before CP: Announcement CP on Media and Democracy. 20 citizens to learn, reflect and adopt resolutions on 3 topics. Expected resolutions to be presented in June to... Context: other CPs in Austria, Ireland, Slovenia and the Czech Republic. As part of the European MeDeMAP research project.
 - Blog posts after CPs: CP stage. Main outcomes of the day.
- **Who:** focus on CP participants and experts (info about organizers and facilitators).
 - Blog post before CP: Presentation of participants selection & diversity. Diversity of experts. Facilitation. WP institution. MeDeMAP.
 - Blog posts after CPs: presentation of the experts of the day. Participants as actors.
- **Where and when:** Country, city or cities. Venue. Dates. Stages.
 - Blog post before CP: contextualization. Details on venue and dates and time. Explain stages.
 - Blog posts after CPs: brief mention of venue and if same place.
- **How:** organization and atmosphere
 - Blog post before CP. Details the audience should know about organization
 - Blog posts after CPs: description of process and atmosphere (quotations of participants?)
- **Why:** purpose

Blog post before CP: national purpose of CP, expected outcomes, what will be done with results. MeDeMAP research project.

Blog posts after CPs: remind the goals of the national CP and how the participants got closer to this goal.

Annex 10: MeDeMAP Task 6.3/6.4 - Research questions

MeDeMAP Task 6.3/6.4 - Research questions (final version 2.1)

(incorporating suggestions from the operationalization proposal in D2.2 and the previous proposals for research questions - earlier versions 1.1, 1.2 and 2.0 from COMMIT and CU, dd. 3.12.2024 and 17.12.2024; final version 2.1 dd. 20.12.2024)

Task 6.3 “Analysis of the sessions and final decision of citizens' parliaments”

- *Goal:* Analysis of the **content/output of the CPs** (the recommendations) and of the **process to generate that content** in the CP sessions
- *Main research question for Task 6.3:* How do the citizen parliaments in the four countries envision the democratic roles of media in their recommendations for future perspectives and in the processes leading to these recommendations?
- *Secondary research questions for Task 6.3:*
 - What articulations of the media's democratic roles did the participants in the CPs prioritise, which were omitted and which received only limited attention?
 - Which recommendations on future perspectives received consensus within the CPs? Which future perspectives were the object of political struggle, and which ideological perspectives structured these differences?
 - How balanced were the power relations that characterized the process of producing the recommendations of the CPs? How was conflict handled during the process? How was collaboration achieved during the process?
 - How are the CPs' imaginaries of the media's democratic roles similar and different in the four countries against the background of their respective political agendas?
- *Outcome:* Deliverable 6.4.: Future roadmap for European media and democracy report (COMMIT)

Task 6.4 “Evaluation of PAR research”

- *Goal:* Analysis of **the construction of democracy and media** in the participatory CP process
- *Main research question for Task 6.4:* How are democracy and media constructed in the participatory process of the four CPs?
- *Secondary research questions for Task 6.4:*
 - How is participation performed in the CPs? Which (sub)processes are forms of minimalist / maximalist participation?
 - How is democracy constructed in the CPs? Which core components are accepted (or not), and how do the citizens in the CPs position themselves towards the relevant political struggles and threats?
 - How are media constructed in the CPs? Which core components are accepted (or not), and how do the citizens in the CPs position themselves towards the relevant political struggles and threats?
 - What are the similarities and differences between the four countries in terms of their performance of participation and their constructions of democracy and media?

Outcome: integrated into Deliverable 2.4: Theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions (CU)

Annex 11: Overview of data gathering, analysis and dissemination

Overview of data gathering, analysis and dissemination for Tasks 6.3/6.4 (and Task 2.4)

By Andrea Sedlaczek and Nico Carpentier

18 January 2025

- *Data to be collected in the CP process:*
 - Final resolutions/recommendations adopted on each of the 3 topics (with votes and expressions of dissent)
 - Minutes of the CP meetings
 - Flipcharts and posters produced during the CP meetings
 - Audio recordings and selective transcripts of plenary discussions
 - Field notes (from ethnographic observers for T6.3 and T6.4)
 - Online surveys after each CP
 - Interviews with a selection of participants after the end of the CPs

- *Background:*
 - D2.1 - Theoretical framework on democracy, participation and representation
 - D2.2 - Operationalization proposals for T6.3 and T6.4
 - Analytical concepts developed in WP3, WP4 and WP5 deliverables

- *Methodology:*
 - Participatory Action Research (PAR) to structure the project (and enrich CP)
 - Qualitative textual or discourse analysis for data analysis
 - Data-gathering methods: textual productions by the participants, transcription of audio recordings, ethnographic observation, interviews, surveys, group feedback analysis
 - Group feedback analysis as closing participatory research component

- *Analysis and outcomes:*
 - National reports with two sections, one for each research question
 - Group feedback analysis of the national reports
 - Aggregated analysis in deliverable D6.4 (on basis of national reports, more section one)
 - Re-theorization in D2.4 (on basis of national reports, more section two)
 - Popularized / accessible version in D6.5 (Leaflets and online guidance on participatory media practices)
 - Academic and non-academic dissemination (see dissemination plan – still to be developed)

Annex 12: Indications for the CP observers' training

Citizen parliament observers' training (v1) - CU

25 February, 9:00 – 15:00, online

Please, read before the training:

Carpentier, N., & Wimmer, J. (2025). *Democracy and media in Europe: a discursive-material approach*. Routledge.

Carpentier N. (2016). "Beyond the ladder of participation: An analytical toolkit for the critical analysis of participatory media processes", *Javnost-The Public*, 23 (1), p. 70-88.

Main structure

- Introduction to the project and to the WP6 research questions
- Introduction to ethnographic research and methods
- The setting of the citizen parliament – The role of observers in the citizen parliament
- Unpacking the WP6 research questions for the observers
 - RQ1 - What to look for
 - RQ2 - What to look for
- Observing and taking notes

Research question 1: How do the citizen parliament participants envision the democratic roles of media in their recommendations/resolutions for future perspectives and in the processes leading to these recommendations?

• *Secondary research questions*:

- a. What articulations of the media's democratic roles did the participants in the CP prioritise, which were omitted and which received only limited attention?
⇒ Reading: Carpentier & Wimmer (2025). Chapter 7. The Roles of (European) Media in Democracy (pp. 52-64)
- b. Which recommendations on future perspectives received consensus within the CP? Which future perspectives were the object of political struggle, and which ideological perspectives structured these differences?
⇒ Reading: Carpentier & Wimmer (2025). Chapter 8 Struggles over Media's Democratic Roles (pp. 64-74)
- c. How balanced were the power relations that characterized the process of producing the recommendations of the CP? How was conflict handled during the process? How was collaboration achieved during the process?
⇒ Reading: Carpentier Nico, 2016, "Beyond the ladder of participation: An analytical toolkit for the critical analysis of participatory media processes", *Javnost-The Public*, 23 (1), p. 70-88.

Research question 2: How are democracy and media constructed in the participatory process of the CP?

• *Secondary research questions:*

- a. How is participation performed in the CP? Which (sub)processes are forms of minimalist / maximalist participation?

⇒ Reading: Carpentier & Wimmer (2025). Part 1. Democracy (pp. 5-41), focusing on pp. 11-13.

- b. How is democracy constructed in the CP? Which core components are accepted (or not), and how do the citizens in the CP position themselves towards the relevant political struggles and threats?

⇒ Reading: Carpentier & Wimmer (2025). Part 1. Democracy (pp. 5-41).

- c. How are media constructed in the CP? Which core components are accepted (or not), and how do the citizens in the CP position themselves towards the relevant political struggles and threats?

⇒ Reading: Carpentier & Wimmer (2025). Part II. Media and Democracy (pp. 44-95).

Annex 13: Examples of publications on the forthcoming CP in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia

Annex 13a: CP in Austria - COMMIT

- Article in daily newspaper Der Standard. 14. Februar 2025, 13:39.
<https://www.derstandard.at/story/3000000257394/buergerinnenrat-ueber-medien-und-demokratie-sucht-noch-buergerinnen>

FORSCHUNGSPROJEKT

"Bürgerinnenrat" über Medien und Demokratie sucht noch Bürgerinnen

Diskussion über Wünsche und Anforderungen an Medienlandschaft

Harald Fidler
14. Februar 2025, 13:39

27 Postings Später lesen

Ein "Bürgerinnenrat Medien und Demokratie", im Original mit Genderstern, soll im Rahmen eines europäischen Forschungsprojekts Wünsche und Bedürfnisse für Österreichs Medienlandschaft entwickeln. Bis 20. Februar können sich Interessierte noch melden, 20 Menschen sollten hier an vier Samstagen mitreden.

Derzeit wirbt der Bürgerinnenrat Medien und Demokratie noch mit Postkarten Teilnehmerinnen und Teilnehmer für die vier Diskussionsrunden.
Verena Hochleitner für Commit/Bürgerinnenrat

SI Etat > Medien International Inland Wirtschaft Web Sport Panorama Kultur Wissenschaft Lifestyle Diskurs

27 Postings

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"Was kann die Politik dazu beitragen, die Qualität von Medieninhalten zu gewährleisten? Welche Möglichkeiten gibt es für Bürgerinnen und Bürger, an der Gestaltung von Medien mitzuwirken? Wie können Medien besser auf die Bedürfnisse von Bürgerinnen und Bürgern eingehen, und was müssen sie tun, um die gesellschaftliche Vielfalt besser abzubilden?" sind einige der Fragen, um die es ab März an vier Samstagen in dem "Bürgerinnenrat" in Wien in der Volkshochschule Floridsdorf gehen soll. Geplante große Themenfelder: Mediensysteme und -regulierung, Repräsentation in den Medien und Partizipation in und durch die Medien.

Die Initiative trägt Commit, das Institut der nichtkommerziellen Communitymedien für Weiterbildung, Forschung und Beratung. Der "Bürgerinnenrat" Medien und Demokratie ist Teil des Horizon-Europe-Forschungsprojekts "Media and Democracy Mapping", das von Kommunikationswissenschaftler Josef Seethaler an der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften koordiniert wird. Insgesamt sind zehn Partner und Länder beteiligt. (Harald Fidler, 14.2.2025)

Links

medemap.commit.at und www.medemap.eu/

BÜRGER*INNENRAT

Demokratie und Medien

Medien stehen vor großen Herausforderungen: Politische Einflussnahme, sinkende Vielfalt, künstliche Intelligenz und fehlende Partizipationsmöglichkeiten bedrohen sie. Im Bürger*innenrat

„Medien und Demokratie“ erarbeiten 20 Vertreter*innen aus unterschiedlichen gesellschaftlichen Bereichen in vier Sitzungen Empfehlungen und Forderungen, um eine demokratische und vielfältige Medienwelt zu sichern. Das europäische Forschungsprojekt wird von Fachleuten des COMMIT, der Social City Academy, des Presse-rats, der Arbeiter- sowie der Wirtschaftskammer und der Universität Wien begleitet. Interessierte können sich bis Anfang Februar bewerben. Die Ergebnisse werden im Juni den Medien, der Politik und der Öffentlichkeit präsentiert.
Bewerbungen bis 20. 2.: medemap.commit.at

NEUE MASSSTÄBE IN DER SCHULISCHEN FÖRDERUNG

Besser Deutsch lernen

Die Deutschkenntnisse der Wiener Schüler*innen zu verbessern, ist das Ziel der acht Projekte im Rahmen der Wiener Mutmillion.

Moderne und wirkungsvolle Sprachförderung – das ist der Schwerpunkt der zweiten Runde der Mutmillion. Die erste Million wurde für Projekte zur Förderung der psychischen Gesundheit von Schüler*innen eingesetzt.

KOMPETENZEN FÖRDERN

Fast die Hälfte der Wiener Taferlklassler*innen verfügt über keine ausreichenden Deutschkenntnisse, um dem Unterricht folgen zu können. Initiativen wie „Sag, was du denkst! Sag, was du fühlst!“ – seit Jänner mit Workshops an 15 Schulen umgesetzt – sollen Abhilfe schaffen. „Jedes einzelne Projekt stärkt nicht nur die Sprach- und Sozialkompetenzen unserer

QR-Code scannen und Video zur Mutmillion anschauen:

Kinder und Jugendlichen, sondern eröffnet ihnen auch echte Perspektiven für eine erfolgreiche und selbstbestimmte Zukunft“, so Vizebürgermeister Christoph

Wiederkehr. Und er fordert bundesweite Maßnahmen wie ein verpflichtendes zweites Kindergartenjahr, um frühzeitig sprachliche Förderung sicherzustellen.

Wien erhielt Access City Award

Mit dem Preis würdigt die EU-Kommission Verbesserungen der Barrierefreiheit. Wien setzte sich gegen 56 Bewerber*innen durch.

O b bei Verkehr, Infrastruktur, im öffentlichen Raum, bei Dienstleistungen oder punkto Information – „die Stadtregierung ist bemüht, Barrierefreiheit in allen Lebensbereichen zu einer Selbstverständlichkeit zu machen“, sagt Bürgermeister Michael Ludwig. Etwa mit der Strategie „Inklusives Wien 2030 – eine Stadt für alle“, die soziale Inklusion forciert. Sozialstadtrat Peter Hacker nahm den Access City Award in Brüssel entgegen.

QR-Code scannen und Video zum Award anschauen:

Die begehrten Trophäen wurden in Brüssel an die Sieger*innen überreicht.

- Post card (©Verena Hochleitner) calling for participation shared as print and online version in Austria

MACHEN SIE MIT IM BÜRGER*INNENRAT MEDIEN UND DEMOKRATIE!

- Bestimmen Sie die Zukunft der Medien in Österreich mit!
- Tauschen Sie sich mit anderen Bürger*innen und Expert*innen aus Forschung und Medien zur demokratischen Rolle von Medien aus!
- Erleben und gestalten Sie Demokratie hautnah!

Entwickeln Sie mit 20 anderen Bürger*innen Empfehlungen und Forderungen zu diesen und weiteren Fragen:

- Was kann die Politik dazu beitragen, um die Qualität von Medieninhalten zu gewährleisten?
- Welche Möglichkeiten gibt es für Bürger*innen, an der Gestaltung von Medien mitzuwirken?
- Wie können Medien besser auf die Bedürfnisse von Bürger*innen eingehen und was müssen sie tun, um die gesellschaftliche Vielfalt besser abzubilden?

Der Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie tagt an vier Samstagen zwischen März und Mai 2025:

22. März, 5. April, 26. April und 17. Mai, jeweils zwischen 10 und 18 Uhr in Wien.

Im Juni 2025 präsentiert der Bürger*innenrat seine **Ergebnisse Medienverantwortlichen, politischen Entscheidungsträger*innen und der breiten Öffentlichkeit.**

Für Ihre Teilnahme erhalten Sie eine **Aufwandsentschädigung**.

Kontakt: COMMIT – Community Medien Institut für Weiterbildung, Forschung und Beratung, Prinz-Eugen-Straße 72 Top 1.5, A-1040 Wien, <https://medemap.commit.at>, **Mail:** medemap@commit.at

Bewerben Sie sich jetzt unter: medemap.commit.at

Grafik & Illustration: Verena Hochleitner

Annex 13b: CP in the Czech Republic - CU

For more publications see <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/news/>

- Deník 17.12.2024 <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/IV-V.pdf>

Deník N – rozumět lépe světu **DENÍK N** Přihlášení Koupit předplatné

Vánoční předplatné Česko Svět Ekonomika Kultura Magazín Podcasty E-shop knihy

17. prosince 2024 9:23 Media

Neexistuje jeden model demokracie. Proč potřebujeme experimenty, které dávají hlas těm nejtišším?

NICO CARPENTIER

Odebírat e-mailem

VAIA DOUDAKI

Odebírat e-mailem

MILOŠ HROCH

Odebírat e-mailem

Občanské parlamenty jsou využívány jako nástroj k „demokratizaci demokracie“. Foto: Adobe Stock

Na sociálních sítích křičí všichni, ale jsou skutečně slyšet? Jak přizpůsobit demokracii tak, aby byly vyslyšeny i hlasy těch nejtišších? Proč je to potřeba v době, kdy také ve střední Evropě sílí autoritářské hlasy, které představují reálné ohrožení demokracie? Na některé otázky mohou pomoci hledat odpovědi občanské parlamenty a shromáždění, v Evropě stále populárnější formy spolupodílení se na demokracii. Přicházejí také do Česka.

Tento text pro vás načetl robotický hlas. Pokud najdete chybu ve výslovnosti, **dejte nám prosím vědět**. Plné znění audioverzí článků je dostupné pouze pro předplatitele Klubu N. **Předplatte si ho také.**

TIP: Souhrn dne podle redaktorů Deníku N. Odebírejte Pointu N s výběrem nejdůležitějších událostí dne s odkazy na zajímavé texty.

Občanské parlamenty a shromáždění jsou hojně využívané nástroje k zapojení občanů do politiky. Ačkoli terminologie může být občas matoucí a tyto experimenty s demokracií bývají nazývány různě, některé principy jsou univerzální. [Databáze deliberativní demokracie](#) (Deliberative Democracy Database) organizace OECD, která zmapovala tyto (a podobné) iniciativy mezi lety 1973 a 2023, čítá více než 700 příkladů. Občanské parlamenty a shromáždění tedy mají dlouhou historii, oblibu si ovšem získaly především v minulé dekádě a tato popularita trvá dodnes – OECD ve svých nejnovějších zprávách dokonce hovoří o „deliberativní vlně“.

Naše vlastní zkušenost (nebo alespoň zkušenost jednoho z nás) sahá právě do minulé dekády, kdy belgická nadace King Baudouin Foundation uspořádala takzvanou občanskou laboratoř, která se měla zabývat velice konkrétním tématem: úhradami zdravotní péče. Na podzim 2014, tedy před rovnými deseti lety, se do práce na tomto tématu pustilo 32 občanů – nejprve se během jednodenního setkání seznámili s problematikou a poté po tři víkendy, během nichž absolvovali řadu debat, školení a poradenství s odborníky, nakonec společně vypracovali seznam kritérií pro hrazení zdravotní péče.

Poslední víkend se nad těmito kritérii znovu sešli a odhlasovali si, která jsou důležitější více a která méně. Výsledkem byl soubor kritérií a podmínek pro veřejné zdravotní pojištění. Jedním z důležitých závěrů byla nutnost vyvážit snahu o blaho pacientů na jedné straně a efektivitu a hospodárnost na straně státu.

Tato občanská laboratoř byla jednak sama o sobě experimentem v politické participaci, tedy spoluúčasti na procesu rozhodování, avšak současně byly debaty, jež v rámci setkání proběhly, a závěry, k nimž účastníci došli, analyzovány samostatným týmem (nezávislých) odborníků. Byl to tedy prostor, kde se potkávala politika a výzkum.

Vznikla tak jedinečná příležitost

KONTEXT

Obsahující parlamenty a shromáždění jsou nejvíce vyvíjenými nástroji ve vzájemně se doplňujících občanských institucích. Ačkoli terminologie může být obtížná, tyto experimenty s demokracií byly inspirovány radikálními principy jako univerzální, decentralizované demokratice (Deliberative Democracy Database) organizace OECD, která zmapovala tyto (a podobné) instituce mezi lety 1973 a 2021, čímž více než 700 příkladů. Občanské parlamenty a shromáždění tedy mají dlouhou historii a oblibu si osvojují v různých částech světa. A tato popularita trvá dál – OECD ve svých nejnovějších zprávách dokonce hovoří o „deliberativní vlně“.

Někdy vlastní zkratka (nebo alespoň zkratka) působí jako překážka. Když se jedná o občanské shromáždění, může být obtížné vysvětlit, jak to funguje. V roce 2014, tedy před rokem deseti let, se do práce na tomto tématu pustilo 12 občanských skupin z celého světa. Každá skupina měla za úkol vypracovat vlastní definici občanského shromáždění. Po několika měsících práce se skupiny sešly a společně vypracovaly společnou definici. Tato definice byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

Podle ní vzniká se nad tímto kritériem zpravidla a odlišností si, které jsou důležitější a které méně. Vytvářením byl součástí kritéria a podstatou pro větší zájem o spolupráci s občanskými institucemi z důležitých zúčastněných a hospodářství na straně státu.

Tato občanská laborator byla jedním z mnoha experimentů v politické participaci, tedy spolupráci na úrovni občanské společnosti, která soustřeďuje lidi dohromady, aby se v rámci určitého problému, a zvláště, když se jedná o občanské shromáždění, mohli společně vypracovat řešení. Tato participace byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

Vznikla tak politická přítomnost podobnosti s občanskými institucemi, které byly během experimentu vyvíjeny a podstatou se byly postupně měnit. Každá skupina měla za úkol vypracovat vlastní definici občanského shromáždění. Po několika měsících práce se skupiny sešly a společně vypracovaly společnou definici. Tato definice byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

Volba, kterou musí učinit každé shromáždění – více či méně – sama. Některé demokratice mají například velmi silnou politickou vedení, zatímco jiné občanské instituce volby osvojují. Praktičtější demokratice je v takových případech často rozlišovat na politicky vedené a demokratice dle občanských institucí, které existují pouze jako občanské shromáždění nebo jeden zprávný, jak by se mohlo zdát. Neexistují žádné pravidla, která by určovala, jak by měly být tyto instituce organizovány.

Někdy ačkoli tato konkrétní občanská laborator byla organizována na výzvu, tato definice občanského shromáždění je v zásadě univerzální a aplikovatelná na různé kontexty. Tato participace byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

KDYZ NIKDO NEVYSLOUČIL
Demokratice je volně zobrazena na rozmezí mezi reprezentací (občanské shromáždění) a občanskými institucemi (občanské shromáždění). Tato participace byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

Současné frustrace přání vzhledem k tomu, že má být nepopulární.
Tato participace byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

Neexistuje jeden model demokracie

NICO CARPENTIER, VAJA DOUDAKI A MILOŠ HROCH
mediální vědci

podobnost s občanskými institucemi a experimentální zřízení občanských institucí do svého repertoáru demokratických nástrojů, heslita volání po zavedení těchto participativních mechanismů, znamená to, že se současně ptáme, jaký druh demokracie vlastně chceme. Předpokládáme, že existuje pouze jeden model demokracie nebo jeden zprávný, jak by se mohlo zdát. Neexistují žádné pravidla, která by určovala, jak by měly být tyto instituce organizovány.

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uplatnění v mnoha různých oblastech společenského uplatnění a na různých úrovních rozhodování. Jedním z argumentů pro participativní formu demokracie je, že v současných vývoje komplexnějších společenských jsou vstříplými povahy občanských a politické apatie. Ačkoli jsou jejich příčiny velmi složité a mnohdy nejasné, s příchodem o nich mluvíme řetězec volby, vzhledem k tomu, že existuje pouze jeden model demokracie nebo jeden zprávný, jak by se mohlo zdát. Neexistují žádné pravidla, která by určovala, jak by měly být tyto instituce organizovány.

demokratické instituce, které byly během experimentu vyvíjeny a podstatou se byly postupně měnit. Každá skupina měla za úkol vypracovat vlastní definici občanského shromáždění. Po několika měsících práce se skupiny sešly a společně vypracovaly společnou definici. Tato definice byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

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Na sociálních sítích (Facebooku, ale zejména na Twitteru) se objevily různé názory na to, jak by měly být tyto instituce organizovány. Některé komentáře byly velmi kritické, zatímco jiné byly velmi pozitivní. Tato participace byla následně použita v různých kontextech, včetně učebnic a odborných článků.

Další zmiňují, že občanské shromáždění pomáhá nastartovat změny v slovenské komunitě ve městě Maribor se konají pravidelně již deset let. Jejich cílem je podpořit nezávislé občanské politické sdružení v obcích. Především je největším úspěchem této iniciativy bylo zavádění participativní tvorby městského rozpočtu v roce 2015 a tuto práci následně převzalo na čtyřech dalších slovenských městských samosprávách.

Také lidstvo – kde se nyní je – má v roce 2022 uskutečnit občanské shromáždění o klimatické správnosti – také zajímavý příklad, jak mohou občanské parlamenty sloužit jako efektivní nástroj občanské politiky. Ve spolupráci s Vozňáčikem, kde jsou komitace o občanských institucích, musí místní vlády rozhodnout, které opatření navržené občanskými shromážděními budou přijata a provedena.

Výše příkladů z různých částí Evropy by mohl pokračovat a probíhat v podobě těchto zvláštních rozprav. První krok se od března do června bude konat občanské shromáždění v obcích a demokratice v Rakousku, Slovensku, Irsku a také České republice. V rámci evropského občanského shromáždění budou diskutovány různé otázky, které se týkají klimatické správnosti a občanských institucí.

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Dobrometr

HLAVNÍ STRANA / ČLÁNKY

Občané rozhodují o médiích. První občanský parlament o médiích a demokracii v Česku hledá dobrovolníky

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V příštím roce se v Rakousku, Slovinsku, Irsku a také Česku budou konat občanské parlamenty o médiích a demokracii. Nejenom z hlediska střední Evropy se jedná o důležitou kontrolu zdravého fungování médií v době, kdy vlády zemí jako Maďarsko nebo sousední Slovensko výrazně omezují nezávislost médií a zvyšují kontrolu nad kulturními institucemi.

Čtete také

Občané rozhodují o médiích. První občanský parlament o médiích a demokracii v Česku hledá dobrovolníky

Osm výjimečných dobrovolníků z Olomouckého kraje inspirovalo svými činy, získali cenu Křesadlo 2024

Mediální vědci a vědkyně z Univerzity Karlovy, kteří organizují občanský parlament o médiích a demokracii v Česku, jsou součástí evropského výzkumného projektu *Mapping Media for Future Democracies (MeDeMAP)*. Ten si klade za cíl zmapovat evropskou mediální krajinu a zjistit, za jakých podmínek plní média demokratické funkce a jaká nebezpečí nebo výzvy (mediální) demokracii v Evropě čekají. Do projektu je zapojeno deset univerzit a výzkumných institucí také z Itálie, Polska, Portugalska nebo Francie.

Výzkumný tým z Centra pro výzkum kultury a komunikace (CULCORC) na Institutu komunikačních studií a žurnalistiky (IKSŽ) FSV UK aktuálně hledá 20 dobrovolníků a dobrovolnic, kteří by se chtěli zapojit do tohoto demokratického experimentu. Občanský parlament (dále jen OP) o médiích a demokracii v Česku bude zasedat mezi březnem a červnem 2025 během čtyř sobot v Praze, Olomouci a Brně.

Annex 13c: CP in Ireland - MIC

- Poster calling for participation shared in Ireland

BE PART OF A NATIONAL CITIZENS PARLIAMENT BEING HELD IN LIMERICK!

MEDEMAP

HAVE YOUR VOICE HEARD and RECEIVE €400 in VOUCHERS
for 4 Days Participation as a thank you!

(Must be available to attend for all four days and be aged 18 +)

Join us to discuss how the media can support democracy
Make resolutions that will be heard in Limerick, Dáil Éireann
and Europe

Meet and talk with other interested people
(lunch etc. provided)

Email MeDeMap@mic.ul.ie to register your interest and find

Funded by
the European Union

Annex 13d: CP in Slovenia – MI

- Poster calling for participation shared in Slovenia

KJE?
Ljubljana

KDAJ?
15. marec,
29. marec,
12. april,
10. maj.

10:00-16:00

**ŽELITE SODELOVATI
NA ZBORU OBČANK_OV
O MEDIJIH
IN DEMOKRACIJI?**

 OBVEZNA PRIJAVA
na povezavi QR kode (levo)
ali preko e-pošte:
tjasa.turnsek@
mirovni-institut.si

prijave zbiramo
do **20. 2. 2025**

**VEČ O ZBORU
OBČANK_OV**
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www.mirovni-institut.si
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MEDEMAP

Mirovni inštitut
Inštitut za medkulturne odnose in politične študije

Financira Evropska unija. Stališča in mnenja, izražena v tem besedilu, so izključna odgovornost avtorjev_je in ne odražajo nujno stališč Evropske unije ali Evropske izvajalske agencije za raziskava. Na Evropska unija niti agencija za njih ne odgovarjata.

ŽELITE SODELOVATI NA ZBORU OBČANK_OV O MEDIJIH IN DEMOKRACIJI?

Med **marcem in junijem 2025** bo Mirovni inštitut organiziral **zbor občank_ov o medijih in demokraciji**.

Če vas zanima obravnavana tema in udeležba, vas vabimo, da se prijavite.

Zbor občank_ov bo potekal ob sobotah na **štirih zaporednih srečanjih v Ljubljani**, okvirno med 10. in 16. uro v teh dneh:

- sobota, **15. marec**,
- sobota, **29. marec**,
- sobota, **12. april**,
- sobota, **10. maj**.

Izbrali bomo **20 udeleženk_cev**, ki bodo po sestavi odražali raznoličnost prebivalstva glede na spol, starost, izobrazbo in druge demografske kazalce.

Obvezno je, da se izbrani kandidati_ke udeležijo vseh štirih srečanj.

Na srečanjih bo poskrbljeno za prigrizke in kosilo, predvideno je tudi simbolično denarno nadomestilo za udeležbo.

Zbor občank_ov je del evropskega znanstveno-raziskovalnega projekta o medijih in demokraciji (MeDeMAP).

Če vas zanima sodelovanje na zboru občank_ov o medijih in demokraciji, se prijavite preko QR kode ali nam pišite na naslov: tjasa.turnsek@mirovni-institut.si.
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OBVEZNA PRIJAVA

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prijave zbiramo
do **20. 2. 2025**

VEČ O ZBORU OBČANK_OV

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in na spletni strani
www.mirovni-institut.si
(projekt MeDeMAP)

Mapping Media for Future Democracies

**WP6: Initial methodological guidelines for CP design and
organization**
Task 6.2 - Methodological guidelines

Laurence Monnot and Helmut Peissl

(DELIVERABLE 6.2 V0)

MeDeMAP - Mapping Media for Future Democracies

Grant Agreement number: 101094984

Vienna, August 2024

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Introduction

Objective and limits

This initial methodological-guidelines document aims to provide a framework for the practical steps that will need to be adopted by the five MeDeMAP WP6 partners who are involved in the stages of the design and organization of the four face-to-face Citizen Parliaments (CP). Another objective is to clarify some notions and to explain the features and principles that will guide the implementation.

Guidelines for the design and organization of the fifth (online) CP will be defined separately.

WP6 Time plan according to Coordination Plan

Please note that this initial version of the methodological-guidelines document is being communicated to WP6 partners as an informal guidance to facilitate the partners' planning, while the research on CP good practices for deliverables D6.1 and D6.2 is still underway. This 'V0 version' deals primarily with the preparation of the CPs (stages 1 and 2 of the steps identified in the "Next steps" section). Information about the collection and analysis of data and the dissemination has been included, but later versions will include more details on these components, but also on the implementation.

"Deliverable 6.2: Design of citizens' parliaments" is scheduled for Month 24 (February 2025). Task 6.2 is based on Deliverable 6.1 ("Research report on successful practice of policy development with citizen parliaments in Europe", scheduled for Month 22, Dec. 2024); both are currently in progress.

References: The design recommendations are based on a still ongoing literature review for D6.1 and D6.2 (mainly CP guidebooks, comparative scholar literature on CPs and evaluation reports of CPs), interviews with CP practitioners and consultations with WP2. They also draw on methodological guidelines from the other WPs. Among the various sources, many themselves refer to the OECD's principles of good practice, which are based on the analysis of 300 examples of assemblies.

Time frame and next steps

7.3.24	1 st WP6-Meeting in Lisbon: presentation of WP6 goals and tasks
8.4.24	2 nd WP6-Meeting on Zoom: presentation of core design features of CP and upcoming WP6 activities
14.5.24	Short questionnaire on national experiences with CPs sent to WP6 partners (objective: clarify national contexts in which CPs will take place & identifying stakeholders)
15.5.24	Rough cost categories for CP's design sent to partners
7.6.24	3 rd WP6-Meeting on Zoom: first findings on CPs' design, main design features of our CPs, next steps
1.8.24	Initial methodological guidelines for CP design and organization
6.8.24	4 th WP6-Meeting on Zoom
31.8.24	Replies to questionnaire expected to be submitted (from WP6 partners)
18-19.9.24	WP6-Meeting slots in Krakow (one closed, one open)
End of September 24	Invite the members of the Support Group in each country. Identification & information of relevant stakeholders
12-14.11.24	WP6-Meeting in Vienna with training in AoH
Oct. to Dec. 24	Recruitment of participants. Book CP locations (and accommodation & catering). Communication: Information of participants. Identify, book and brief external facilitator if needed. Invite experts for training. Finalizing training videos (with MeDeMAP experts, 12 minutes each).
January-March 25	Confirm registration of participants Confirm experts' participation Public communication advertising CP
March-June 25	CP implementation Data collection
June-Sept. 25	Data selection & translation. Production of national reports by WP6 partners (CP organisers).
Autumn 25	Official presentation of CP recommendations (national level)
End of project (Jan. Feb. 26)	Participation of CP members in presentation in Brussels (part of WP7 dissemination)

Part 1: Citizens Parliaments and Participatory Action Research: definitions, features and principles

This section presents elements that will feed into D6.1, the research report on successful practices of policy development with citizen parliaments in Europe.

Citizens' Parliament (CP)

In academic literature, the generic term most often used is "deliberative mini-publics" or sometimes "citizens' assemblies". For our project, we will prefer "Citizens' Parliament" or CP, which is the term used in the Grant Agreement.

Definition

For Gaşiorowska, quoting Escobar & Elstub (2017), "(A) mini-public (is) an institution consisting of randomly selected citizens who are representative of their population with regard to different demographic characteristics (such as age, gender, ethnicity, education, etc.) and who deliberate on a given issue through facilitated discussion, on the basis of evidence and advocacy provided by experts" (Gaşiorowska, 2023, p. 2).

Dahl, also quoted by Escobar & Elstub, emphasized the collective deliberation on public issues and defined "minipopulus" as an assembly of citizens, demographically representative of the larger population, brought together to learn and deliberate on a topic in order to inform public opinion and decision-making (Escobar & Elstub, 2017, p. 6).

Podgorska, quoting Chambers and Curato, underlines the participatory process and its "impact on public policy-making by adding a civic perspective to the decision-making process" (Podgorska, 2024, p. 152).

Main features

The generic term "mini-public" encompasses all types of deliberative people assemblies, regardless of their size, duration, organization of meetings, facilitation and outcomes, including Citizens' Assemblies, Citizens' Juries or panels, Consensus Conferences, Planning Cells, Deliberative Polls, etc. Confusingly, the "mini-public" concept is also used for other types of (small) public gatherings, e.g., at public screenings, which is another reason why we prefer CP.

According to the academic literature review done so far, a CP could be defined as

- a forum of selected citizens who are representative of a population,
- expressing an informed opinion on the basis of evidence and perspectives provided by experts,
- a process of collective deliberation,
- producing an outcome in the form of resolutions, recommendations or assessments on issues of public interest (e.g., media and democracy).

Overview of different CP models (draft for D 6.1)

CP form	History	participants	Compact / over WE	# days	Stages	Outcome	Selection	Addressee
Citizen assembly	2002, Canada	100-160	8-14 mo over WE	20-30	Learning/ information consultation deliberation adoption	detailed recommendations	random + self selection	public institution
Citizens' jury /panel (original)	1971, USA, Crosby	12-26	compact	2-6	Learning/ information consultation deliberation adoption	collective position report	random selection	sponsor mass media
Citizens' jury /panel	Canada, Australia	36-45	over WE	2-6	Learning/ information consultation deliberation adoption	collective position report	random selection + correction	
Citizens' Council (Bürgerrat)	Vorarlberg, Austria Jim Rough	15	compact	1-2	(information) consultation deliberation adoption			
Consensus Conference	1987 Danish board of technology	10-25	compact over WE	7-8 10-30	Information deliberation	collective position report	random + self selection	parliament mass media
Planning cell	1970, Germany Dienel	100-500 25-50	compact	3-5	Information deliberation	survey opinions collective position report	random selection	sponsor mass media
Deliberative polls	1994, USA, Fishkin	100-500	compact	2-3	Information deliberation	survey opinions	random selection	sponsor mass media

Principles

Based on the analysis of 300 representative deliberative practices (initiated by public institutions) the OECD (2020) has published a list of “Good Practice Principles for Deliberative Processes for Public Decision Making”, which are commonly retained in most practical guidebooks issued by associations supporting CPs.

These principles are

- Have a purpose: “The objective should be outlined as a clear task and is linked to a defined public problem. It is phrased neutrally as a question in plain language.”
- Accountability: “There should be influence on public decisions.”
- Transparency: The deliberative process should be announced publicly. The process design and all materials should be available to the public. The funding source should be disclosed.
- Inclusiveness: Inclusion should be achieved by considering how to involve under-represented groups.
- Representativeness: “The participants should be a microcosm of the general public. (...) In some instances, it may be desirable to over-sample certain demographics during the random sampling stage of recruitment to help achieve representativeness.”
- Information: Participants should have access to a wide range of accurate, relevant, and accessible evidence and expertise. They should have the opportunity to hear from and question speakers.
- Group deliberation: “Participants should be able to find common ground to underpin their collective recommendations to the public authority. This entails careful and active listening, weighing and considering multiple perspectives, every participant having an opportunity to speak, a mix of formats that alternate between small group and plenary discussions and activities, and skilled facilitation.”
- Time: “To achieve informed citizen recommendations, participants should meet for at least four full days in person (...). It is recommended to allow time for individual learning and reflection in between meetings.”
- Privacy: “There should be respect for participants’ privacy to protect them from undesired media attention and harassment, as well as to preserve participants’ independence (...). Small group discussions should be private. The identity of participants may be publicized when the process has ended, at the participants’ consent. All personal data of participants should be treated in compliance with international good practices, such as the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).”

Source: OECD. (2020). Innovative citizen participation and new democratic institutions: Catching the deliberative wave. Highlights. Paris: OECD Publishing, pp. 9-11

Participatory Action Research (PAR)

The use of PAR for WP6 is anchored in the Grant Agreement.

The function of WP6, as defined in the Grant Agreement, is the one hand to create a thematic junction with other WPs (this junction is called “Supply meets demand”) and on the other hand to open up the research process to a wider public. For the implementation of the CP, the GA prescribes a PAR approach, which is defined as “*an approach within the broad field of responsive science (...) based on open cooperative work and sharing of knowledge.*” (Part B, p. 15).

Giving a voice to concerned citizens within a research project is in itself a participatory practice, that is related to PAR, but PAR requires more. The philosophy of participatory action research is based on involving citizens in the research of which they are the subjects, so as (1) to make the most of their insights and (2) to involve them in the design and the decision-making process.

How does PAR apply to the design and implementation of WP6 CPs?

A PAR approach will impact WP6 in various ways:

-The CP’s successive stages (learning, deliberating, adopting resolutions) should enable a circular and iterative process, following the PAR cycle of observing, reflecting, acting, evaluating and modifying;

-Participants should, within the general framework of the CP theme and the three main topics (media systems, representation and participation in and through the media), be given the space to develop subtopics themselves.

The participants will decide on the first day what kind of outcome (i.e. recommendations or resolutions) they want to achieve and what wording they prefer. The facilitation process should also have a participatory dimension;

-We should not forget to try to add a participatory dimension to the recruitment of participants (engaging, e.g., the Support Group in the recruitment process).

A circular and iterative modus

As emphasized by CU in D2.2, PAR implies a circular and iterative modus and a focus on deliberation. Applied to the CP’s design, this means that the different stages (e.g. learning, deliberating, adopting resolutions, ...) need to empower the participants, using the PAR cycles. We should be aware that this creates a tension with the limited time available (4 days).

Facilitation should pay attention to the needs for iterative steps and space for deliberation, for instance when first formulating the proposed recommendations ... while still respecting the tight time schedule. The opportunity for participants to express their dissenting opinions online after the CP sessions on days 2, 3 and 4 also creates a link with PAR.

The most vital component, though, is the general CP time plan, where during day one, for each of the three main topics (structure, representation and participation), the participants will decide on the subtopics (which will then, most likely, produce the recommendations /resolutions according to the expected outcome they will have defined on Day 1). At the start

of CP days 2, 3 and 4 (which will each focus on one main topic), these lists of subtopics will be placed on the agenda again, and finalized (by the participants) in the morning sessions of days 2, 3 and 4. This will empower the participants to take control of the agenda as much as possible (within the main framework set by the WP6 team).

Where and to what extent can participants be involved in the design process?

As pointed out by CU in D2.2, there will be a tension between CPs purposes (adopting resolutions on three complex topics, within one general theme) and an extensive PAR approach involving the CP participants in the design process. Nevertheless, participation *in* and *through* the CPs will occur at several levels.

Inclusiveness and participation in the CP process:

-The **Support Group** should include representatives from diverse organizations, making suggestions for participants, but also giving feedback on the set-up.

-The **Art of Hosting facilitation** method will ensure that all CP participants will be able to express their voice or request knowledge support and participate equally in the collective deliberation and adoption of resolutions.

-Between meetings, participants should have the opportunity **to provide feedback or express diverging opinions**. (The minutes of the daily session, with the accepted resolutions, will be sent to the participants soon after each day session with a link to a form which enables them to express diverging opinions with particular resolutions, if they want to do so). The diverging opinions will be documented in an annex to the resolutions.

-**Participation in the reformulation of the topics discussed:** As pointed out in D2.2 pp. 35-37, "*Some of the key characteristics of the citizen parliaments in the original project proposal limit the number of themes that these meetings can handle*" (for instance the number of meetings is set at four).

Moreover, the choice of the three main topics (media systems, participation in the media, representation in the media) is guided by the results of WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5, and had to be predefined. However, participants will need to be autonomous in deciding on the subtopics for each of the main topics, and on developing resolutions in relation to these subtopics.

Other PAR aspects (and some additional limits):

-While the **rules for the procedures** will be adopted by the participants, the walkthrough and the rules for adopting resolutions (qualified majority with expression of dissent) will be fixed beforehand.

-The **outcome** of the CP in the form of the resolutions or recommendations adopted will be published and communicated. An advocacy system for their implementation will be set up, thus enabling participation *through* the CP. WP6 will support this process, at the national and European level.

-Respect for privacy: The participants will sign a consent form framing the use of their data and ensuring compliance with the GDPR during the process and follow-up stages. The collection of data for further analysis and the dissemination must respect their privacy, but also private deliberations (e.g. no video recordings of small groups, etc.).

Part 2: Practical design and steps

This section presents elements that will feed into D6.2, Design of citizens' parliaments.

CP Design for WP6: main features

What model for our CPs? The design of WP6 CPs will be tailor-made, taking into account our objectives and resources, as well as local contexts. It will consider the lessons learned from the evaluation reports of previous CP experiences and will borrow features from different models.

	Design features	Details
Number of participants	20	From focus groups & through open calls
Number of sessions & duration	4 x 1 day sessions (8 hours/day including breaks)	
Meeting dates	Between March and June 2025	If possible (according to local calendars) every 2-3 weekends. Preferably on Saturdays, avoiding holidays.
Theme and Topics	Main theme: media & democracy 3 topics: media systems (supply and regulation), representation in the media, participation in & through the media Subtopics for each of the 3 topics to be decided by participants	
Proposed walkthrough	Day 1: CP rules of procedures, CP goals; learning phase: introduction to main theme and 3 topics, (first) drafting of sub-topics Day 2, Day 3, Day 4: learning phase (training & questions), confirming (or changing) sub-topics for the day 2 topic, deliberation, elaboration of resolutions/recommendations, adoption of resolutions/recommendations After Day 2 & Day 3: online opportunity for dissenting opinions (with accepted resolutions) Day 4: additional slots for (1) dissenting opinions, and (2) general CP wrap-up and conclusion	
Location(s)	Physical space for deliberation in large and small groups.	Accessible with public transport for all. Consider catering and overnight.

CP walkthrough more in detail

Day 1	<p>Arrival and get-together</p> <p>Host welcome, check-in, overview of the CP's process</p> <p>Participants agree on CP objectives & procedures, and establish discussion rules</p> <p>Learning phase: Introduction to the main theme and the 3 topics, Q&A session.</p> <p>Discussion on the sub-topics for each of the three topics (output: three lists of sub-topics).</p> <p>Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings</p>
Day 2	<p>Arrival and get-together.</p> <p>Learning phase: topic 1 (Media systems)</p> <p>Confirming list of sub-topics for topic 1 (or modifying it)</p> <p>Deliberation: Discussion & development of proposals</p> <p>Decision-making: Voting on the resolutions/recommendations</p> <p>Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings</p>
After Day 2	<p>Creation of Minutes, with all resolutions</p> <p>Online opportunity for dissenting opinions</p>
Day 3	<p>Arrival and get-together.</p> <p>Learning phase: topic 2 (Participation in the media)</p> <p>Confirming list of sub-topics for topic 2 (or modifying it)</p> <p>Deliberation: Discussion & development of proposals</p> <p>Decision-making: Voting on the resolutions/recommendations</p> <p>Wrap-up & outlook for the next meetings</p>
After Day 3	<p>Creation of Minutes, with all resolutions/recommendations</p> <p>Online opportunity for dissenting opinions</p>
Day 4	<p>Arrival and get-together</p> <p>Learning phase: topic 3 (Representation in the media)</p> <p>Confirming list of sub-topics for topic 3 (or modifying it)</p> <p>Deliberation: Discussion & development of proposals</p> <p>Decision-making: Voting on the recommendations/resolutions</p> <p>Face-to-face opportunity for dissenting opinions</p> <p>CP wrap-up and conclusion</p>
Separate event (Autumn 2025)	<p>Official presentation of resolutions/recommendations at national level</p> <p>Presentation at European level (as part of WP7 dissemination)</p>

Next steps in details

Tasks to achieve until December 2024:

- Anchoring CP's objectives and identifying relevant stakeholders according to the local context
- Constitute a Support Group
- Recruitment of 20 participants
- Information and communication on CP to stakeholders, participants and the public
- Identifying experts and practitioners for the learning phase
- Creating MeDeMAP training videos (and subtitling them)
- Determine locations
- Setting up facilitation modus and a full walkthrough

1. Identify stakeholders and set up a Support Group

Anchor CP's objectives and identify relevant stakeholders according to the local context.

The questionnaire sent out to WP6-partners in May aimed to establish the local context to identify the stakeholders to be involved in the process, who should also become the addressees of the resolutions/recommendations adopted by CP participants.

Stakeholders supporting the CPs could be representatives of media & media world (unions, press councils, users' associations), political decision-makers involved in the field of media & democracy at large, relevant NGOs.

The formation of a Support Group involving around 5 to 10 stakeholders will increase the participatory component of the project and reinforce its legitimacy. Stakeholders from the media world will bring different perspectives, but also relevant NGOs and social movement actors can actively contribute. We would recommend not to include politicians in the Support Group.

The Support Group is a body representing civil society. Its task is to provide support according to the capacities of the individual members:

- in the recruitment of participants/experts
- to communicate about the CP and disseminate the results to civil society and/or decision-makers
- for access to disadvantaged groups/ensuring diversity.

The support group should ensure legitimacy; therefore, membership should be transparent.

The number of meetings and exact form of support should be adapted locally.

Steps:

-Identify the stakeholders from the media sector and civil society: actors working in the media sector, impacted by the issues or supporting those affected... The group should provide a strategic vision of the issue, while reflecting different perspectives.

-Establish the rules for setting up a Support Group (composition, tasks, meeting rules & frequency...) according to your possibilities. The WP6 partners can decide whether the group members take this role in an honorary position, or whether they will receive a small financial compensation (e.g., honorary in Austria, financial compensation in the Czech Republic).

As formulated in a working document addressed by CU to prospective members of the Support Group (called Advisory Council in the Czech case) for the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy,

“The function of the Advisory Council will be consultative. The members of the Council are not expected to be involved in the management of the Citizen Parliament, or to be present at the meetings of the Citizen Parliament itself.

The members of the Council will offer their advice and guidance mostly in an asynchronous mode (e.g. through notes or email communication), and in two online meetings. In practice, they will be asked to provide feedback in core documents pertaining to the design of the Citizen Parliament. They will also be asked to suggest names of potential participants for the Citizen Parliament, and/or distribute the call for participants in their organization.” (working document “Advisory Council for Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy”, CU).

2. Recruitment of CP’s participants

We aim at recruiting 20 participants. A higher number should be recruited to create a reserve list. Some of them may be volunteers from the focus groups organized for WP5, the others will be recruited through different calls (public calls and promotional campaigns, or through calls forwarded by partners).

Recruitment from the WP5 focus groups (FG): Some partners added this in the general information provided to the FG participants, or gave the FG participants a separate leaflet. (see draft information flyer, Annex 1)

Recruitment through calls: different options

- identify the best networks to relay your call (stakeholders & NGOs, media, social networks).

- launch a public call for participants via your website, or other media

Selection criteria

The Grant Agreement provides (on p. 12) a description of the “implementation of citizens’ parliaments in local contexts of the countries covered” (Task 6.2): *“The sociodemographic composition of the citizens’ parliaments should be guided by the idea of a kind of “audience council” representing the interest of readers, listeners, viewers and online media users across various sociodemographic groups.”*

The selection criteria will be inspired by those for the focus groups defined by IULM for WP5. Also, the WP5 questionnaire for FG incorporates demographical and behavioral criteria. Please refer to Deliverable 5.3 (p. 9-10), which can be adapted to your own context as for the FG previously. CU has already developed an intake questionnaire for its CP candidates, which includes several questions relating to political opinion, in order to balance the composition of the panel. After making a pre-selection, CU plans to interview selected candidates to assess their motivation to participate in the CP, and to further ensure diversity.

As with the FGs, we will not be inviting minors (for logistical reasons) but will aim for a **balanced group composition with heterogeneous socio-demographic characteristics and diverse ideological perspectives**. It is up to each WP6 partner to decide autonomously exactly which disadvantaged people to include, but all partners will need to be sensitive to ensuring that also disadvantaged people are included. Please see Deliverable 5.3 (p. 8 to 10). The participants are expected to not know each other (except from their WP5 focus group participation, if they volunteered through this channel). They should not exercise a function in a political party. Participants should express commitment in the CP, in order to participate in constructive deliberations.

“As a qualitative research, participants sample is not representative of the whole society, but of personal perspectives on these issues, which are useful in understanding people’s motivations and needs. The sample will be as large as possible, with an equal gender balance and heterogeneous socio-demographic characteristics. Moreover, special attention should be granted to gender differences and the perspective of disadvantaged groups. The definition within which teams should operate when recruiting disadvantaged people follows the guidelines of the European Institute for Gender Equality.” (Deliverable 5.3, p. 8)

“(..) The goal is to include in the study sample “those who, compared to the general population, are subject to social exclusion, discrimination and violence”. As each country and national context will have different issues and disadvantaged groups, the decision to adopt such a general definition is precisely designed to not limit the

target group, leaving each team to decide autonomously which disadvantaged people to include.” (Deliverable 5.3, p. 8)

Public call for participants via the organizational website or a blog, or other media

Each partner will need to develop a communication strategy for the search for participants. The organizational website or blog could be used to launch the call, but these calls can also be distributed through your networks and other means (like leaflets, media ads, etc.).

For instance, in Austria, candidates volunteering to take part in the CP will register online using Lime Survey. CU is using a tool developed by the EU for the survey. This online registration tool should guarantee data protection.

An example of a basic **information leaflet**, which could also be used as a call to citizens, is presented in Annex 1. The wording is expected to be adapted to your specific context. We suggest that you carefully “test” the reception of the text with your team, stakeholders and various advisors before publishing it.

Compensation for participants

CP participants will receive a compensation for their time in cash or vouchers. The amount and type of compensation will be decided by each partner (e.g., COMMIT will offer 50 EUR per meeting.)

3. Identifying experts and practitioners for the learning phase

Each of the WP6 partners (with the support of their Support Group) will identify local experts and media practitioners, who will be invited to contribute to the learning sessions of the CP.

Objective of the learning sessions: Experts and media practitioners will explain the concepts and will provide overviews of the different positions and perspectives on one (or more) of the three topics. Their fact-based information will contribute to informed deliberation of the participants. They should be selected on the basis of their expertise and the diversity of their perspectives.

Three categories of experts:

- Local knowledge experts: scholars or individuals with specialist scientific, technical or legal knowledge
- Practitioners: concerned representatives from interested groups or institutions, who provide evidence advocating a certain perspective.
- MeDeMAP WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 speakers on each of the three topics (video conversations, with subtitles in local language)

During the learning phase, participants will have the opportunity to raise questions and ask the experts present for additional information.

We recommend a variety of learning formats: panel discussions, Q&A, video and different types of presentations face to face and online.

Invited experts are expected to address participants as a non-informed audience.

4. Location for CP meetings

To find the right venue, the WP6 partners will take into consideration the costs, accessibility, comfort and symbolism. Consider obtaining stakeholders' support.

Criteria to consider:

- Accessibility: the venue must be easily accessible to all participants by public transport.
- Sufficient space for deliberations (with possibilities for break-out sessions).
- Correct acoustic conditions for audio recordings
- Catering facilities

5. Communication

The communication will address stakeholders, CP participants and a wider public.

Each partner will develop its own out-reach-plan to reach decision-makers and achieve a maximum of impact with the CP-decisions and outcomes.

Start planning and implementing public communication to inform about the CP project as early as possible.

We recommend having a separate webpage on your organizational website with information about the CP and ways to volunteer. For instance, CU has set up a dedicated webpage for MeDeMAP at <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/OP/>. This webpage includes a FAQ for citizens interested in participating in the CP. This kind of webpage "*validates the assembly's existence in the public's eye, gives it a tangible trail, and serves a functional purpose as a communication platform.*" (Nowak, Z., 2021, October 20).

Other options include press releases, interviews, messages on various social networks, etc. Consider partnership with media and/or NGOs.

Blogs and blog posts

WP6 third deliverable (D6.3) is a blog. The Grant Agreement states p. 28 that "*the process of implementing citizens' parliaments will be accompanied by blog posts and online debates on the EPALE platform to enable further participation from the educational sector*".

MeDeMAP Coordination Plan (D1.1) precises p. 23 that “*each partner is expected to contribute at least one blog post*”.

COMMIT will have the WP6 blog on its website. All WP6 partners are expected to contribute at least six postings to this blog, with one post before the first CP, one post about each of the four days, and one on the national dissemination event.

It is not explicitly stated in the GA that each partner must have their own blog to cover the CP process, but partners are welcome to do so. Of course, blog contributions (on the COMMIT blog) can also be published directly on your website in local languages.

6. Facilitation

Although the decision on whether or not to hire a facilitator can be made after the WS training in November, we recommend inquiring about facilitators beforehand. (If needed, please ask COMMIT for information about the international network of AoH facilitators.)

The role of a facilitator is to guide participants through the CP in a “*process that flows step by step, with a set of activities that move people through getting information, understanding information, coming up with ideas, reviewing, prioritising and refining*”. (Democracy Fund, 2019, p. 167)

Facilitators ensure that participants have an equal say and that the discussions are respectful and fair. Facilitators help the participants “*make better use of the knowledge and ideas that they collectively possess, they must be neutral in terms of content.*” (liDP, 2020).

It is not important that facilitators know about the topic but they should still be involved in the design.

The Art of Hosting

Our research has shown that, for our purposes and in our contexts, particularly as we deal with complex topics and aim to produce resolutions/recommendations through informed deliberations in just four days, the Art of Hosting method is the most appropriate. It provides for a participatory process of deliberation and decision-making, while effectively guiding participants through the various stages and respecting the criteria of inclusivity:

“The Art of Hosting is a highly effective way of harnessing the collective wisdom and self-organizing capacity of groups of any size. Based on the assumption that people give their energy and lend their resources to what matters most to them – in work as in life – the Art of Hosting blends a suite of powerful conversational processes to

invite people to step in and take charge of the challenges facing them." Retrieved from artofhosting.org

Facilitation is a skill that requires training and experience. *"Co-facilitation works very well because two or more facilitators can attend to both task (getting the job done, staying focused on the group's purpose) and maintenance (ensuring each group members is being heard, that the group is working harmoniously)."* (Carson, 2017, p. 3).

Training in the Art of hosting

A two-day training in the Art of Hosting (AoH) will be integrated into the WP6 Workshop, which will take place in Vienna from November 12-14, 2024.

The training will produce an introduction to facilitation and help **design a more detailed walkthrough for facilitating the CP**, from getting the participants to know one another, learning, deliberating, finding common ground, developing recommendations, coming to the adoption of resolutions for the 3 topics and wrapping up the results.

In the course of this training, we'll also be testing the video conversations with MeDeMAP WP leaders on the three topics (media systems, media participation, media representation) as learning material.

Part 3: Data collection and partners' deliverables

During the implementation of the CPs, WP6 partners will collect data that will serve for the next phases of the MeDeMAP project. Furthermore, the outcome of each CP, in the form of final resolutions/recommendations will be published and disseminated.

Purpose of data collection: analysis by WP6 and WP2

The data collected during the CP will nourish the reports for

- Task 6.3: Analysis of the sessions and final decisions of citizens' parliaments, focus: the content of the recommendations.
- Task 6.4: Evaluation of PAR research, focus: the generation of the content
- Task 2.4: Theory-driven re-analysis of the project's interventions, focus: analysis of the participatory process & the construction of media and democracy

Data collected

The following data will be collected:

- the final resolutions/recommendations adopted on each of the 3 topics (with votes and expressions of dissent),
- minutes of the CP meetings,
- audio recordings and selective transcripts of discussions (no video recording), posters, flip charts observation and field notes
- online surveys
- interviews with a selection of participants (after the end of the CP)

Data selection, translation and pre-analysis

The data selected for further analysis will be transcribed and translated into English by each partner. Depending on the partners, the persons involved in data collection may be their own staff or volunteers/interns. CU proposes to train them online.

After the CP, each partner will write up a **national report** with these two sections:

- analysis of the recommendations and, of their development process,
- analysis of the participatory process

Dissemination of final resolutions/recommendations

The **final resolutions/recommendations** are the result of the CP and, as such, are not simply data to be analyzed, but also the outcome of a participatory citizen process, which will need to be made available to the public and disseminated to relevant stakeholders for further advocacy. This will take the form of

- dissemination of reports with resolutions/recommendations, e.g., through

presentations to (political) institutions at national levels and later in Brussels in January or February 2026

- dissemination of experiences and analysis on blog posts on COMMIT website

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Erwin Mayer, Mehr Demokratie.at (Austrian Branch) <https://mehr-demokratie.at/>

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Guter Rat für Rückverteilung (privately initiated Citizens' Council for Wealth Distribution) Cilli <https://guterrat.info/en/>

Annex 1: Draft information flyer

Take part!

Austrian Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy

How can the media better serve democracy?

- Which functions should pro-democratic media play in our society to strengthen democracy?
- How should the Austrian media landscape be regulated to guarantee high-quality content?
- How can the media become more representative of the diversity of views?
- How can we foster more citizen participation in the media?

20 citizens learn, reflect, deliberate and adopt recommendations to strengthen the democratic role of the media in Austria.

The recommendations will be presented to *policy makers, regulators, and civil society organizations dealing with media policy but also to representatives of the media sector itself.*

When? The Austrian Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy will meet **four Saturdays** between **March and June 2025**.

Initiative and organization

The Austrian Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy is organized by the Community Media Institute [COMMIT](#) *in cooperation with...* as part of the European [MeDeMAP](#) research project.

Citizens' parliaments are democratic instruments that give citizens a greater voice by carefully organizing deliberations on a particular social issue and helping them to formulate decisions that contribute to the improvement of society.

To take part in the Austrian Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy send an email to... cp.media@commit.at

or register online ([link to online form](#))

**Annex 2: WP5 Screening questionnaire for focus groups
recruitment(D5.3.Methodological protocol, p. 13)**

1. Age:

- 18-24 y/o
- 25-35 y/o
- 36-44 y/o
- 45-54 y/o
- 55-65 y/o
- Over 65 y/o

2. Gender:

- Man
- Woman
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

3. Education level:

- No title
- Elementary school
- Middle school
- High school
- Degree or Master's degree
- Postgraduate
- Prefer not to say

4. Where do you live?

5. How interested are you in political news?

- Very interested [3]
- Fairly interested [2]
- Not very interested [1]
- Not interested at all [0]

6. How much time do you spend on average reading or watching political news on a typical day?

- Less than 10 minutes [0]
- 10-30 minutes [1]
- 30 minutes - 1 hour [2]

More than 1 hour [3]

7. Have you participated in any political elections (e.g. voted) in the last 5 years?

Yes [1]

No [0]

8. Are you part of a political party, movement or organisation (like NGOs) ?

Yes [1], please specify

No [0]

9. Have you participated in demonstrations, protests, petitions or other political activities (including online) in the last 12 months?

Yes [1]

No [0]

10. How would you best describe your political views?

Prefer not to say

Extreme Left

Left

Slightly left

Center

Slightly right

Right

Extreme Right

Annex 3: CU Screening questionnaire for the recruitment of candidates

Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy – Survey questionnaire

We appreciate your interest in joining the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy!

Filling out this questionnaire will help us to recruit participants for the citizen parliament.

Please note that you are expected to answer all questions (leaving questions unanswered will not allow you to complete and submit the filled-out questionnaire).

The organiser of the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy is CULCORC, the Culture and Communication Research Centre at the Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism at Charles University, as part of the European MeDeMAP research project.

You can find more information about the organisation of the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy here: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/>

1. What is your age?

- Less than 18 y/o
- 18-24 y/o
- 25-35 y/o
- 36-44 y/o
- 45-54 y/o
- 55-65 y/o
- Over 65 y/o

2. What is your gender?

- Man
- Woman
- Other
- Prefer not to say

3. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Elementary school
- Middle school
- High school
- University/ Higher education
- Master's degree
- PhD
- Other (please describe) _____

4. Where do you live? (city, town or village) (if you live in different places, please add the location where you spend most of your time)

.....

5. What is your current socio-professional status? (You can select more than one option. For example: Self-employed + student, etc.)

- Employed

- Self-employed
- Unemployed
- Student
- House person
- On parental leave
- Retired
- Other (please describe) _____

6. If you are employed, what is your professional activity?

7. How interested are you in the news?

- Very interested
- Fairly interested
- Not very interested
- Not interested at all

8. How much time do you spend on average reading, watching or listening to the news on a typical day?
(It doesn't matter which medium you use.)

- Less than 10 minutes
- 10-30 minutes
- more than 30 minutes , but less than 1 hour
- 1 hour or more

9. Have you participated in any political elections (e.g. voted) in the last 5 years?

- Yes
- No

10. Are you a member of any political party or political movement?

- Yes
- No

11. Are you engaged in the activities of any other organisation (e.g., NGO, civil society organisation, activist organisation)?

- Yes. If Yes, in what kind of organisation? _____
- No

12. Have you participated in demonstrations, protests, or petitions (including online) in the last 12 months?

- Yes
- No

How much do you agree with the following statements? Select one option for each statement.

13. Being Czech is the most important part of my identity.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

14. The migration of people from other parts of the world is enriching for the Czech society.
- Completely agree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Completely disagree
 - I Don't know
15. The world is already complicated enough, and it's better that we maintain our traditional values and our traditional family and gender roles.
- Completely agree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Completely disagree
 - I Don't know
16. Each one of us should focus on taking care of our lives and defending our own interests; the other people's problems should not be our priority.
- Completely agree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Completely disagree
 - I Don't know
17. We can overcome social problems, if we express solidarity to our fellow humans and help one another.
- Completely agree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Completely disagree
 - I Don't know
18. Authorities and institutions have the responsibility to support our needs and help us solve our problems.
- Completely agree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Completely disagree
 - I Don't know
19. The taxes and contributions for high-income individuals and companies should be increased to provide for public education, healthcare and pensions.
- Completely agree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Completely disagree
 - I Don't know

20. Water, energy and main natural resources should be under state control.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

21. The government should invest more resources to reduce social and economic inequalities.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- I Don't know

22. The government should invest more resources on national security.

- Completely agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neutral [neither agree nor disagree]
- Somewhat disagree
- Completely disagree
- Don't know

23. How much do you trust the following institutions, for their beneficial role in society? Select one option for each institution.

a. Government

- Completely trust
- Somewhat trust
- Neutral [neither trust nor distrust]
- Somewhat distrust
- Completely distrust

b. Media

- Completely trust
- Somewhat trust
- Neutral [neither trust nor distrust]
- Somewhat distrust
- Completely distrust

c. Science

- Completely trust
- Somewhat trust
- Neutral [neither trust nor distrust]
- Somewhat distrust
- Completely distrust

24. Please, write down your name and your contact information (email address or telephone number), so that we can reach you about the citizen parliament recruitment.

Do note that if you do not provide this information, we will not be able to reach you and we cannot consider you a potential participant of the citizen parliament.

Name:

Email:

Telephone number :.....

Thank you for filling out the questionnaire! We will get back to you in due time to inform you about the recruitment of participants for the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy.

The information that you provide in this questionnaire will be collected only for the purposes of recruiting participants for the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy and will not be used for any other purpose nor will it be shared with third parties.

All data related to the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy is handled in compliance with GDPR. In case you wish to have your data removed or altered, or have concerns about stored data, please contact dr. Miloš Hroch at milos.hroch@fsv.cuni.cz.